

D4.1: Specification of TBOM Structure

PROJECT	
Project Number	101120962
Project Acronym	RESCALE
Project Title	Revolutionised Enhanced Supply Chain Automation with Limited Threats Exposure
Start Date	01.10.2023
Programme	HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-02
DELIVERABLE	
Deliverable Type	R - Document Report
Workpackage	WP4
Deliverable Lead	Dell (EISI)
Editors	Alan Barnett (Dell EISI)
Contributors	ISI, UPRC, AEGIS, INT, CBRL, DIE, UNSMPF, ICERT, BNR, STS
Dissemination Level	PU - Public

Abstract

Deliverable D4.1 outlines the structure of the Trusted Bill of Materials. This document provides a state-of-the-art overview, format selection, the structure specification, lifecycle and distribution mechanisms for the Trusted Bill of Materials, as well as security considerations. The specification in this deliverable is of great importance to several other tasks within RESCALE project. The information in this document also describes the initial core features of the Trusted Bill of Materials.

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101120962

Document Revision & Quality Assurance

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Revisions

Version	Date	Partner	Overview
0.1	25/01/2024	Dell	ToC
0.2	21/02/2024	Dell	Sections structured
0.3	12/06/2024	Dell, All	Base content
0.7	23/09/2024	Dell, All	Finished draft
0.8	29/09/2024	Dell, AEGIS, ISI	Reviewer comments and text update
0.9	05/10/2024	Dell, All	Comments addressed
1.0	12/10/2024	Dell	Final version
1.1	19/07/2025	Dell	Revised Version - Sections 2.2, 3.2 and 7.1 have been added to address the Review Report comments

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List of Abbreviations

- ABAC** Attribute-Based Access Control. 58
- ACL** Access Control List. 59
- API** Application Programming Interface. 14, 20, 24, 60
- BOM** Bill of Materials. 9, 10, 12–14, 18–21, 24, 28–30, 34–39, 41, 42, 45, 46, 62, 64
- BOV** Bill of Vulnerabilities. 30, 33
- CAD** Computer-Aided Design. 19
- CD** Continuous Development. 20, 23
- CDX** CycloneDX. 13–15
- CI** Continuous Integration. 20, 23
- CLI** Command Line Interface. 20, 25
- CPE** Common Platform Enumeration. 14, 15, 21, 22
- CSV** Comma Separated Values. 25, 27
- CVE** Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures. 24–26, 28
- CVS** Concurrent Versions System. 22
- CVSS** Common Vulnerability Scoring System. 25–28
- DAC** Discretionary Access Control. 59
- DL** Deep Learning. 12, 13
- DSCG** Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee. 27, 33, 34, 40–43, 46–48, 64
- GDPR** General Data Protection Regulation. 52
- HBOM** Hardware Bill of Materials. 29
- HTML** HyperText Markup Language. 25
- IEC** International Electrotechnical Commission. 15, 17, 29
- IoT** Internet of Things. 18
- ISO** International Organization for Standardization. 15, 17, 29
- JSON** JavaScript Object Notation. 10, 12, 14, 15, 17, 18, 25, 26, 29, 32–35, 40, 46, 60, 64, 65
- MAC** Mandatory Access Control. 59

MFA Multi-Factor Authentication. 59

ML Machine Learning. 12, 13

MVP Minimum Viable Product. 9, 46, 64

NIST National Institute of Standards and Technology. 21

NLP Natural language processing. 12

NPM Node Package Manager. 23

OCI Open Container Initiative. 20

OWASP Open Worldwide Application Security Project. 14, 20, 24, 25, 29, 30

PDF Portable Document Format. 25

PII Personally Identifiable Information. 62

PURL Package Uniform Resource Locator. 36, 42

RBAC Role-Based Access Control. 58

RCS Revision Control System. 22

RDF Resource Description Framework. 15, 17

RL Reinforcement Learning. 12

SARIF Static Analysis Results Interchange Format. 26

SBOM Software Bill of Materials. 13–15, 17, 19–21, 24, 25, 30, 33–36, 46, 48

SDK Software Development Kit. 61

SDLC Software Development Lifecycle. 20

SotA State of the Art. 11, 12, 60, 64

SPDX System Package Data Exchange. 12–17, 19–21, 28–31, 46

SSCG Static Supply Chain component Guarantee. 27, 33, 34, 39–41, 43, 46–48, 64

SVN Subversion Versions System. 22

SWID Software Identification. 12–15, 17, 18, 29

TBOM Trusted Bill of Materials. 9–13, 18, 29, 30, 32–43, 46–64

UI User Interface. 25, 26

URI Uniform Resource Identifier. 14, 21

URL Uniform Resource Locator. 14–16, 33, 36, 40, 42, 44–46

URN Uniform Resource Name. 32, 35

UUID Universally Unique Identifier. 32, 35

XLSX Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet. 15, 17

XML Extensible Markup Language. 12, 14, 15, 17, 34

XSD XML Schema Definition. 12

YAML Yet Another Markup Language. 15, 17

ZKP Zero-Knowledge Proof. 60–62

1 Introduction

The RESCALE project aims to advance secure-by-design supply chains, focusing on automating the evaluation of software and hardware components to mitigate vulnerabilities. RESCALE strives towards creating robust cybersecurity audit processes and developing secure systems with reliable assurances. Through systematic analysis and improvement of each layer in computing systems, RESCALE introduces new tools and methodologies across the entire supply chain. This document outlines the project's progress by detailing the structure of the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM), along with the background and relevant considerations.

1.1 Scope & Contribution

Deliverable D4.1 specifies the structure of the TBOM along with additional information such as state-of-the-art overview and lifecycle, and is the result of extensive design work.

This deliverable provides the RESCALE project, in particular Work Package 4 (Tasks T4.2 and T4.3), with vital information necessary to implement the TBOM and initiate development on a first-version Minimum Viable Product (MVP). While the TBOM structure is sufficiently detailed to support development work, since this deliverable was released largely before the development phase, unforeseen challenges are likely to emerge. Any necessary adjustments to the TBOM will be summarized in a future deliverable..

1.2 Relation to Work Packages, Deliverables, and Activities

Deliverable D4.1 is an output of T4.1, within WP4. It also has some relevance to Work Packages 3 (WP3) and 5 (WP5). This work is closely associated with the establishment of a secure supply chain, with the TBOM being a core component of this effort.

1.3 Contribution to WP4 and Project Objectives

Deliverable D4.1 is a crucial output of WP4 T4.1, which contributes to Objective O4.1: Define the Trusted Bill of Materials structure for WP4. This work will provide input into T4.2 and T4.3 in order to design and implement how the security assurance will be incorporated into the TBOM as well as how the Trust Assurance will handle the TBOM. In addition, D4.1 also contributes to the project objective 3, to provide a Trusted BOM approach that will infuse trust in software and hardware supply chain and promote trusted updates, by defining the TBOM structure.

1.4 Structure of the Document

The rest of the deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 2 State of the Art Analysis:** This section provides the necessary context and related background, which underpinned the creation of the TBOM structure by providing the necessary state of the art by providing a relevant short summary of D2.3 as well as provide some additional state of the art specifically for this work.
- **Section 3 BOM Format Selection:** This section provides the necessary reasoning behind the BOM format selection for the TBOM structure.
- **Section 4 Trusted Bill of Materials Structure:** The next section details the structure of the TBOM, forming the crux of the document by specifying all the fields and formats.
- **Section 5 TBOM Lifecycle:** The TBOM structure is followed by the TBOM lifecycle depictin the possible states in which it can exist, including a mix of lifecycle states and vulnerability states which have been combined into an integrated flow.
- **Section 6 TBOM Distribution Mechanism:** The next section discusses the use of ledger technologies, specifically distributed ledgers, smart contract technologies and externalized assets are described in this section in the context of facilitate distribution of the TBOMs.
- **Section 7 TBOM Security:** Technologies for the security, privacy preservation and integrity of the TBOM are discussed in this section. This section's primary goal is in explaining the potential security technologies whose output is accommodated in certain TBOM sections, as well as collating information for future deliverables.
- **Section 8 Conclusion & Future Steps:** Finally, this section concludes the deliverable by providing a summary of the work as well as discussing the next steps.
- **Section 9 Annex:** This section presents an example TBOM JSON program in full .

2 State of the Art Analysis

This section, summarizes the collected SotA from Deliverable D2.3 to provide context for the rest of the work. In addition, a SotA literature review approach [10] was used to collate the background information discussed herein. This approach involved six methodological steps applied in sequence these being:

- *Determine the initial research question:* This was effectively predetermined by the objective of the deliverable, and is summarized as "what is needed to specify a trusted bill of materials"
- *Determine the timeframe:* The timeframe, in this case, was already predetermined by the RESCALE project schedule, and ran until project month 12.
- *Finalise the research question:* The research question did not deviate from its initial form.
- *Develop a search strategy to locate manuscripts:* The search strategy for this work was relatively basic, and involved combing literature repositories for material relevant to the topics presented in this work. Primarily, the "Google Scholar" search engine was utilized to locate papers by inputting keywords pertaining to the topic in a given section. These keywords are identified as relevant to the research question under a specific topic and used to locate relevant documents, for example under the "TBOM distribution mechanism" topic, in Section 6, keywords such as "ledger" and "blockchain" were utilized.
- *Analyses:* This entails the researchers reading the accumulated literature to extract relevant items and gain knowledge to either support or contradict decisions in their work, or inform design and development. For this deliverable the authors of specific sections analyzed literature related to that section, and did not perform analysis on sections which they were not contributing to.
- *Oversight of researcher interpretation of literature:* This is generally implemented as a "bias review", or similar, to highlight potential conflicts of interest. This is particularly important in scenarios such as a research paper comparing proprietary platforms, where bias could occur if one of the authors is an employee of one of the producing companies. For this deliverable it was determined to use the internal review process of two institutions in the consortium, other than the deliverable lead, to review the work and perform this check as part of the review.

2.1 D2.3 SOTA Overview

The SotA analysis presented in D2.3 provides an extensive evaluation of current technologies and methodologies pertinent to the RESCALE project, especially in relation to software and hardware supply chain security. Key outcomes from D2.3 that are relevant to the development of the TBOM as specified in D4.1 include:

1. Static and Dynamic Code Analysis

- **Static Analysis:** The SotA analysis identifies significant advancements and gaps in static code analysis tools. Most current methods rely on Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques for analysing source code. However, there is potential for integrating newer Machine Learning ML and Deep Learning DL models to improve accuracy and reduce false positives. The Static Analysis output will form one important part of the group of documents which enable the TBOM to operate, as this involves the security testing of the code-base of a component being represented by the TBOM, and a section of the TBOM in this specification is dedicated to the Static Analysis output.
- **Dynamic Analysis:** Existing dynamic analysis tools often depend on synthetic data for evaluation. RESCALE aims to bridge this gap by evaluating these tools on large real-world systems, providing insights into their effectiveness in practical scenarios. Dynamic analyses include Fuzzing and Security Testing. The use of ML for fuzzing is highlighted as a promising area, combining classical ML and Reinforcement Learning (RL) to generate more effective fuzzing inputs. This approach can significantly improve the identification of vulnerabilities in both software and hardware components. Dynamic analysis forms another important part of the document set which enable the TBOM, as it shows elements the security test results of compiled binaries of a component being represented by the TBOM, and a section of this specification is dedicated to it.

2. Blockchain and Trust Mechanisms

- Blockchain technology is identified as a key enabler for enhancing the security and trust of Bills of Materials (BOMs). However, scalability challenges, high transaction costs and the need for hybrid permissioned-permissionless systems are noted as significant barriers.
- The integration of blockchain with TBOM is proposed to ensure the authenticity and integrity of BOM data, leveraging cryptographic trust mechanisms to inspire user confidence.

Building on the findings from D2.3, the Specification of the TBOM Structure in D4.1 addresses the following points:

1. Enhanced TBOM Design

- **Standardization:** Adoption of existing BOM standards such as System Package Data Exchange (SPDX), CycloneDX, and Software Identification (SWID), with necessary modifications to incorporate additional security and trust attributes specific to the TBOM.
- **Data Formats:** Use of standardized data exchange formats (JSON, XML/XSD) to ensure interoperability between different BOM tools and platforms.

2. Background for Security and Trust Enhancements

- **Blockchain Integration:** Implementing blockchain technology to store TBOM data, ensuring immutability and verifiability of the information. This includes designing smart contracts to automate the validation and updating of TBOM entries. In this deliverable we list any findings which will likely support task T4.3.

- **Continuous Security Assurance:** Development of mechanisms for continuous security assessment and validation of TBOMs, integrating runtime monitoring and automated updates based on emerging threats and vulnerabilities. This deliverable collates any information found during this work which is likely of use to task T4.2

3. Interoperability and Automation

- **Tool Integration:** Building converters to switch between different BOM formats, facilitating seamless interoperability across various platforms and tools used within the supply chain. This deliverable mentions findings in this topic discovered during background research.
- **Automated Security Testing:** Enhancing static and dynamic analysis tools with advanced ML/DL techniques to provide more accurate and comprehensive security assessments of software and hardware components. This topic is also mentioned in this work, with findings provided as potentially useful background for future deliverables.

By addressing these areas, D4.1 aims to advance the state of the art in supply chain security, ensuring that the TBOM structure developed under RESCALE meets current needs and anticipates future challenges in a rapidly evolving threat landscape.

2.2 Mapping RESCALE Requirements

The relevant technical requirements addressed by the TBOM technologies are provided in the following list:

- **TR041: TBOM Lifecycle Management:** *The ledger infrastructure must enforce maintenance protocols to keep the TBOM information up to date.*
This TR is addressed in sections 5 and 5.1 of this document
- **TR043: TBOM Generation - merging information:** *TrustOR must be able to gather all the required information for the creation of the TBOM from WP3 components (SBOMs, HBOMs, SSCGs, DSCGs, as well as a number of specialised reports and guidelines describing the results of the security test procedures that have been performed for every component in the TBOM).*

This TR is addressed by the provision of the TBOM specification in this document.

2.3 Standard BOM formats

Accurate identification of software components is crucial for identifying potential security vulnerabilities, and BOMs can greatly assist with this. There are three main, open-source, Software Bill of Materials SBOM formats which are the most commonly used presently [55, 29, 36, 56]. These are the SPDX [49], CycloneDX (CDX) [44] and SWID tags [22]. Of these three SBOMs, CycloneDX and SPDX are the most commonly adopted [56]. The following subsections will provide detail on these SBOM formats.

2.3.1 CycloneDX (CDX)

The CycloneDX (CDX) lightweight BOM specification enhances software security and component analysis in supply chains. It communicates software component inventories and relationships and is an open-source Open Worldwide Application Security Project (OWASP) standard launched in 2017. CDX aims to create an automatable, security-focused SBOM standard, integrating existing specifications like Package URL, CPE, SWID and SPDX license IDs. SBOMs in CDX format can use XML, JSON or Protocol Buffers (protobuf). CDX tracks the dynamic nature of open-source components, including lineage, ancestors, descendants and variations, with unique attributes like commits and patches. The project also provides a catalog of community-supported tools that align with this standard.

CDX SBOM Available Attributes:

- *BOM Metadata:* tools used, supplier, manufacturer, & described software, component, firmware, or device.
- *Components:* first-party & third-party software components type, identity, license, copyright, hashes, pedigree, provenance, and modifications. Components can form nested assemblies with their own supplier info. Digital signatures may be applied.
- *Services:* external APIs the software calls, including endpoint URIs, authentication & data flow details. Digital signatures may be applied.
- *Dependencies:* direct & transitive relationships among components & services.
- *Compositions:* inventory & relationship completeness, labeled as complete, incomplete, first-party only, third-party only or unknown.
- *Extensions:* extension points for new capabilities & specialized future use cases.

CDX Use Cases

- Inventory of software components & services, ensuring license compliance
- Vulnerability analysis, remediation, & other security tasks
- Software supply chain risk assessments & attestations
- Provenance and pedigree, including traceability of modifications
- Verifying integrity of signed components, assemblies, & the SBOM
- Portable file-based formats for build-time creation and distribution, & efficient machine-to-machine binary formats

CDX Key Features

- Simple, prescriptive object model for easy adoption
- Open source standard with permissive, commercial-friendly license

- High automation potential, integration across various development ecosystems
- Supports multiple component identity standards; Package URL, CPE and SWID (tag ID or complete SWID documents)
- Risk-based approach to standards development for rapid delivery of core functionality
- Extensible specification allowing rapid prototyping of new capabilities for specific industry needs

CDX Future Directions

- Incorporate community and Industry Working Group feedback to guide the standard's future
- Development of extensions, including auditing, formulation & vulnerability extension enhancements
- Continuously improve core specification, yearly releases tracked via GitHub milestones

2.3.2 Software Data Exchange Package (SPDX)

The SPDX specification, an ISO/IEC standard launched in 2010, communicates SBOM information including components, licenses, copyrights, and security details in various formats. SPDX facilitates the sharing of human-readable and machine-processable software metadata, enhancing collaboration and data accuracy in the software supply chain.

SPDX offers a common metadata exchange format for software packages to minimize duplication and redundancy. It supports the collection and sharing of data for software products, components, files, and code snippets in formats such as RDF/XML, XLSX, tag-value, JSON, YAML and XML. The specification continuously updates to accommodate new use cases while ensuring backward compatibility, with contributions from technical, business, legal and security professionals.

The SPDX specification outlines the necessary sections and fields for creating a valid SPDX document. However, not all sections are mandatory; only the creation information section is required. The document creator can then select the relevant sections and fields to describe the software and metadata information they intend to share.

SPDX Document Sections

- *Creation Information:* Mandatory for each document, providing details for compatibility (version numbers, license, authors, etc.).
- *Package Information:* Describes products, components, project sources, tarball contents, etc., grouping related items. Packaging files is optional.
- *File Information:* Summarizes a file's metadata, including name, checksum, licenses and copyright.

- *Snippet Information:* Optionally used to denote content within a file that originates from another source, indicating partial file copying.
- *Other Licensing Information:* Covers custom or proprietary licenses not included in the SPDX License List.
- *Relationships:* Describes the various ways documents, packages, files, and snippets are related, supporting 43 relationship types with extension capability.
- *Annotations:* Created during document reviews to add extra information or store additional details not covered by other categories.

SPDX Use Cases:

- Describing system components and their relationships
- Tracking intellectual property, licensing and copyright of software components
- Conducting software supply chain risk assessments and component verification
- Listing software distribution contents
- Tracing executables to source files and snippets
- Inventorying container contents
- Associating Common Platform Enumerations, Software Heritage persistent IDs, and Package URLs with specific packages for enhanced security analysis with packages for security analysis
- Identifying code origins embedded in files

SPDX Key Features:

- Artifact verification using hash values
- Support for intellectual property and licensing details
- Scalable model from snippets and files, to packages and OS distributions
- Integration with package reference and security systems
- Logical partitioning and linking of documents for complex systems

SPDX Future Directions:

- Integrating vulnerability information during SPDX creation, including details on remediation and exploitability status, in alignment with the Vulnerability-Exploitability eXchange working group.
- Enhancing representation of pedigree and provenance to support discussions on chain of custody.

- Strengthening relationships and integrity checks for interactions.
- Introducing elements in future SPDX specifications to accommodate currently unrepresented use cases.

Each document can be represented using a full data model implementation and identifier syntax, enabling exchange between formats (RDF/XML, tag-value, XLSX) and formal validation. Version 2.2 introduced JSON, YAML, and XML formats, and added support for “known unknowns” from the original SBOM framing document. Further details are available in Appendix III of the SPDX Specification and on the SPDX website.

2.3.3 Software Identification Tags (SWID)

Software Identification Tags (SWID) are standardized metadata formats used to uniquely identify software products [22]. SWID tags are standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) under ISO/IEC 19770-2 [21]. These tags help organizations manage and track software assets across various stages of their lifecycle, from installation to retirement. SWID tags contain detailed information about software products, making it easier for IT asset management, security and compliance processes.

SWID tags can function as an SBOM by offering identifying information for software components, detailing files and cryptographic hashes of their artifacts, and including provenance details about the tag and software creators. Tags can link to other tags to represent dependency trees. Generating SWID tags during the build and packaging process allows for the automatic creation of a SWID tag-based SBOM when the software component is packaged.

Types of SWID Tags

The SWID specification defines four types of SWID tags: primary, patch, corpus and supplemental.

- *Primary Tag*: A SWID Tag that identifies and describes a software product is installed on a computing device.
- *Patch Tag*: A SWID Tag that identifies and describes an installed patch which has made incremental changes to a software product installed on a computing device.
- *Corpus Tag*: A SWID Tag that identifies and describes an installable software product in its pre-installation state. A corpus tag can be used to represent metadata about an installation package or installer for a software product, a software update, or a patch.
- *Supplemental Tag*: A SWID Tag that allows additional information to be associated with a referenced SWID tag. This helps to ensure that SWID Primary and Patch Tags provided by a software provider are not modified by software management tools, while allowing these tools to provide their own software metadata.

All four tag types are utilized at different stages of the software lifecycle, and support software management processes that depend on the ability to accurately determine where each software

product is in its lifecycle. For example, before the software product is installed and while the product is being deployed, a corpus tag provides information about the installation files and distribution media (e.g., CD/DVD, distribution package). Next, a primary tag is installed with the software product (or created later) to uniquely identify and describe it. Supplemental tags are generated to enhance primary tags with additional site-specific or extended information. When a new patch is applied to the software product, a new patch tag is provided, supplying details about the patch and its dependencies. As a software product is upgraded to a new version, new primary and supplemental tags replace existing tags, enabling timely and accurate tracking of updates to software inventory. Upon removal of the software product, relevant SWID Tags are removed.

SWID Use Cases:

- Controlling which software is allowed or prohibited within an environment,
- Identifying vulnerable software on endpoints,
- Ensuring that installed software is properly patched,
- Preventing installation of unauthorized or corrupted software,
- Preventing the execution of corrupted software.

SWID Future Directions

- SWID tags are formatted in JSON.
- A lightweight representation called CoSWID is undergoing standardization.
- CoSWID is a Concise Binary Object Representation (CBOR) based binary format for SWID tag information.
- It is intended for constrained IoT use cases.
- More information on CoSWID can be found below.

2.4 BOM Exchange Formats

The question of which proper exchange format to use for the TBOM is debatable depending on multiple factors such as language features, support and even researcher preference. It was deemed prudent to create a comparison matrix of these formats to compare them in terms of one of the most important facets: BOM interoperability. It was noted that JSON was compatible with all three major BOM formats, and JSON was compatible with two of these major formats.

JSON was preferred over JSON, in brief, as JSON requires fewer tags than JSON, needing just a single tag name. It is transportation-independent, allowing data retrieval without XML-HttpRequest, and can include methods for improved procedural handling. JSON works across domains without the need for proxy servers. Moreover, as will be discussed later, SWID was not selected as the BOM standard format for the TBOM.

Language	CycloneDX	SPDX	SWID
XML	X	X	X
JSON	X	X	
RDF-XML		X	
XLSX		X	
tag-value		X	
YAML		X	
Protobuf	X		

2.5 Existing Tools Related to TBOM

The landscape of BOM management is evolving rapidly, with advanced tools and technologies enhancing traditional methods. Some of those tools are commercial while other are available as open-source solutions. Key capabilities that should be considered when looking for an SBOM tool include:

- **Automated generation of SBOM,**
- **Identification of all software components** used in an application, including their versions and dependencies,
- **Continuous monitoring of the software components** used in an application to detect any changes or updates and provide alerts as necessary,
- **Integration with existing tools,** such as vulnerability scanners and application security testing (AST) tools, providing developers with a more comprehensive view of potential security risks,
- **Reporting and analysis** to provide insights on potential security risks associated with the software components used in an application, enabling developers to prioritize and address vulnerabilities efficiently,
- **Scalability** to manage large volumes of software components across multiple applications,
- **The ability to work with standard formats** such as SPDX and CycloneDX to enforce interoperability and flexibility,
- **Support and training resources** to help developers get the most out of the tool.

Comprehensive list of open source tools which support generation of SPDX format is given at [48] and similarly, there is a list of open source tools [18] supporting CycloneDX format. Here are mentioned only some of the current tools and platforms used in the industry:

OpenBOM[38] is a modern cloud-based BOM management software that offers a collaborative environment where teams can create, share, and manage BOMs and related data in real-time. OpenBOM integrates seamlessly with various Computer-Aided Design (CAD) systems, allowing users to import and synchronize BOMs directly from their design software. The platform supports comprehensive features such as inventory management, change tracking, and

cost analysis. OpenBOM's user-friendly interface and powerful data management capabilities help organizations improve their product development processes, reduce errors, and enhance collaboration across different departments and stakeholders. Although OpenBOM offers paid plans, it also provides a free tier suitable for individuals and small teams.

OWASP Dependency-Track[\[42\]](#) is an open-source platform that enables organizations to identify and reduce risk in the software supply chain. It is designed to track and manage SBOM and vulnerabilities in software dependencies. Particularly, it consumes and analyzes CycloneDX BOMs. By integrating with various vulnerability databases and sources (e.g. NVD, GitHub Advisories, Sonatype OSS Index, etc.), Dependency-Track ensures that organizations are informed about known vulnerabilities affecting their software components. The platform facilitates the tracking of dependency versions, licensing, and security advisories, helping organizations maintain compliance and secure their software supply chain. The platform has an API-first design and is ideal for use in CI/CD environments.

Synopsys Black Duck [\[51\]](#) is commercial solution and it offers tools for generating and managing SBOMs as part of its software composition analysis solutions. It provides comprehensive reports on the open source components used, their licenses, and associated risks. It can export SPDX and CycloneDX reports, with standard or custom fields, to provide application transparency and align with customer or industry requirements. It integrates with software development lifecycle (SDLC) tools to automate SBOM generation and continuously monitor SBOM dependencies for existing or newly discovered risk.

OriginTrail [\[39\]](#) is a decentralized knowledge graph platform designed to bring transparency and trust to various industries by enabling the secure sharing and verification of data across supply chains. OriginTrail is particularly known for its application in supply chain management, though its underlying technology can be applied to a wide range of use cases. By using blockchain it can ensure the traceability and integrity of BOMs.

Syft [\[6\]](#) is a open-source CLI tool and library for generating a SBOM from container images and filesystems. It supports common container formats like open container initiative (OCI), Docker, and Singularity and automatically detects Linux distribution. It support conversion between different SBOM formats, such as CycloneDX, SPDX, and Syft's own format. Syft binaries are provided for Linux, macOS and Windows.

The CycloneDX Generator (cdxgen) [\[15\]](#) is the official OWASP SBOM tool. It supports a huge variety of programming languages, including popular ones like C/C++, JavaScript, Java, Python and more obscure languages like Haskell. It comes with a CLI that can scan locally or as part of a CI/CD pipeline and an API server that exposes a BOM endpoint to check the SBOM on demand. As its name implies, the output format is CycloneDX.

SPDX SBOM Generator [\[25\]](#) automates the generation of SBOM in the widely-used SPDX format. The tool supports various programming languages and frameworks, including Java, Python, Go and Node.js, and users can generate SBOMs for both source code and binaries. The tool is open-source and community-driven.

Codenotary [\[14\]](#) is a software supply chain security solution helping organizations manage their SBOMs and secure their SDLC by using blockchain technology to create a tamper-proof and auditable record of the components and dependencies. It supports open-source and proprietary codebases and integrates with various development tools and platforms. It also offers detailed reporting and analysis capabilities, making it easy to track the provenance and usage

of all components within an application.

Fossa [23] solution automatically detects and catalogs all open-source components used in the application and generates a detailed SBOM other in CycloneDX or SPDX format. It also offers continuous monitoring, alerting developers to any changes in the components used in their codebase and integrates with popular tools such as GitHub, Bitbucket and Jira, making it easy for DevOps teams to manage SBOM within their existing workflows. It is best to be used by software development teams using a wide range of programming languages and frameworks. However, this is a commercial solution.

2.6 Ledger & Blockchain SOTA (ICERT, EISI)

Ledger & Blockchain SOTA (trust, e.g., off-chain components, smart contracts, validation, revocation). This section may be moved to D4.3.

2.7 Versioning Formats

Versioning formats are essential for managing and tracking changes in software components, ensuring compatibility, and maintaining security. In the context of the Bill of Materials (BOM) structure, effective versioning allows for accurate identification and management of software parts. In this section, we explore different versioning formats including Common Platform Enumeration (CPE), Semantic Versioning (Semver), and so on.

2.7.1 Common Platform Enumeration (CPE)

Common Platform Enumeration (CPE) is a standardized method used to identify and describe software, hardware, and firmware. Managed by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), CPE provides a naming structure that helps to categorize IT products.

A CPE Name defines a set of related platform types, effectively grouping them into "buckets" that share a common name. The specific relationship between these buckets and external entities is determined by the data producer. For example, security configuration guides for Windows XP might be tagged differently by various producers: one might use a comprehensive set of CPEs for all known versions, updating as necessary, while another might simply use "Windows XP" without specifying version applicability. Both tagging methods comply with CPE standards, but users need to consult the guide authors for precise applicability details [12].

Basic Structure A CPE Name is structured as a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) and starts with the prefix 'cpe:'. It includes up to three major parts, each beginning with a slash and potentially containing multiple elements (representing named hardware or software components of the platform) separated by semicolons. The initial slash is mandatory, while the second and third slashes are optional if their respective parts are empty, as illustrated in Figure 1 [11].

```
cpe:/ {hardware-part} [ / {OS-part} [ / {application-part} ] ]
```

Figure 1: CPE Name Basic Structure

Component Syntax The structure of a CPE name typically includes the vendor, product, version, update, edition, language, and other relevant attributes. Figure 2 shows the basic syntax of a CPE Name.

```
cpe:/ {part} : {vendor} : {product} : {version} : {update} : {edition} : {language}
```

Figure 2: CPE Name Structure

2.7.2 Semantic Versioning

Semantic Versioning (SemVer) [53] is a versioning scheme that aims to convey meaning about the underlying changes in a release. It uses a three-part version number in the format of MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH, which indicates the scope and impact of changes made. The rules of SemVer are as follows:

- MAJOR version increments when there are incompatible API changes.
- MINOR version increments when functionality is added in a backwards-compatible manner.
- PATCH version increments when backwards-compatible bug fixes are made.

2.7.3 Calendar Versioning (CalVer)

CalVer uses the date to create version numbers, often in the format 'YYYY.MM.DD' or 'YY.MM' [13]. It reflects the release date, making it easy to understand the age of a release. It also provides a predictable schedule for releases.

2.7.4 Revision Control System (RCS) Versioning

Revision Control System (RCS) versioning uses a series of numbers separated by dots to indicate major and minor changes, often seen in documents or in systems like Concurrent Versions System (CVS) and Subversion Versions System (SVN). It reflects major and minor revisions and provides detailed version history (granularity).

2.7.5 Alphanumeric Versioning

Alphanumeric versioning combines numbers and letters to create a version identifier. This can include pre-release identifiers and build metadata. The base version objects only allow a

sequence of numeric values, which does not align with the version labeling used by some software. This module, however, enables the specification of versions using a particular sequence of alpha, beta, release candidate, release, and patch labels instead of strictly numeric versions [27]. They are sorted in ascending order, as seen in Table 1:

Table 1: Meaning of Alphanumeric Versioning

Version	Meaning
1.3a	1.3 alpha release
1.3b	1.3 beta release
1.3b2	1.3 second beta release
1.3rc	1.3 release candidate
1.3rc2	1.3 second release candidate
1.3	1.3 final release
1.3pl	1.3 first patch release
1.3pl2	1.3 second patch release

2.7.6 Identifier-Based/Git Versioning

Identifier-based versioning, often referred to as Git versioning, uses unique identifiers from version control systems like Git to specify versions. This format is particularly useful in environments where exact build reproducibility and traceability are critical. Identifier-based versioning uses unique identifiers such as Git commit hashes to version releases. The version identifier typically includes the following components:

- Tag: A human-readable version tag (optional).
- Commit Hash: A unique identifier generated by the version control system.
- Additional Metadata: Optional information like branch names or build numbers.

For example, in "v1.0.0-8-gd7c3a4e", 'v1.0.0' is the tag indicating a major release, '8' indicates that there have been 8 commits since the tagged version, and 'gd7c3a4e' is the short commit hash representing the specific state of the code.

2.7.7 Microsoft Versioning

Microsoft uses a versioning scheme with four numbers separated by dots. There are different versioning schemes, such as [32]:

- major.minor[.build[.revision]]
- major.minor[.maintenance[.build]]

These version numbers are generated during the build/CI process. During CD/release, components are pushed to a component repository like NuGet, NPM, or Docker Hub, where a history

of different versions is maintained. With each build, the version number is incremented at the last digit. Updating the major or minor version indicates changes to the API/interfaces/contracts:

- Major Version: A breaking change
- Minor Version: A backward-compatible minor change
- Build/Revision: No API change, just a different build

2.7.8 Ubuntu Versioning

Ubuntu uses a versioning scheme based on the year and month of the release, typically in the format YY.MM. For example, Ubuntu 23.10 was released in October 2023. Consequently, version numbers for future releases are provisional; if the release is postponed to a different month (or even year) than initially planned, the version number will change accordingly. Additionally, they use the term LTS, or 'Long Term Support,' for their releases, indicating that LTS versions are the 'enterprise grade' releases of Ubuntu and are the most widely used. Approximately 95% of all Ubuntu installations are LTS releases [54].

2.8 Security Test Results Reports

A Security Test Result Report is a comprehensive document that provides a detailed summary of the tests performed, the processes involved, and the outcomes. These reports are typically customized based on the type of security test conducted and offer valuable insights into the security posture of a system, application, or network. In the context of BOMs, the report summarises findings, including vulnerabilities, risks, and recommendations identified during the security assessment or testing process.

Security test results are documented in a structured and methodical format, emphasizing both clarity and detail. The core sections of the report typically include an executive summary, which outlines key findings, a methodology section that describes the testing methods and tools used, and a findings section where vulnerabilities are categorized by severity (critical, high, medium or low). Each vulnerability is documented with a detailed description, steps to reproduce it, evidence such as screenshots or logs, and recommended remediation actions. Additionally, the report should include a prioritized remediation plan with suggested follow-up steps to ensure that it is actionable for developers and stakeholders

2.8.1 Existing tools for Test Result Reports

Many of the tools mentioned on subsection 2.4 not only generate SBOMs but also produce security test reports based on the analysis of those SBOMs. These reports typically include findings on vulnerabilities, license compliance issues, and overall risk assessments. Below is an overview of some of these tools that generate security test reports.

OWASP Dependency-Check [41] generates detailed reports highlighting identified vulnerabilities in dependencies. The reports include CVE identifiers, descriptions of the vulnerabilities,

severity ratings based on CVSS scores, and recommendations for remediation. Reports can be exported in multiple formats such as HTML, JSON, JSON, and CSV.

OWASP Dependency-Track[\[42\]](#) focuses on continuous monitoring of software components and dependencies, rather than one-time scans like OWASP Dependency-Check. The reports generated by OWASP Dependency-Track provide detailed insights into vulnerabilities detected in the SBOM, with severity ratings often based on CVSS scores. These reports may also include information on licensing risks for open-source components, ensuring compliance with licensing obligations. Additionally, OWASP Dependency-Track offers dashboards and graphical reports that display the overall project health, including the number of vulnerabilities detected, their severities, and historical trends

OWASP Defectdojo [\[40\]](#) is a DevSecOps platform that simplifies security management by consolidating and centralizing results from multiple security tools. It improves efficiency by merging findings, tracking false positives, and removing duplicates. The platform integrates with JIRA, generates reports and metrics, and supports traditional pen testing management. Primarily, DefectDojo functions as a vulnerability tracking system, providing traceability between projects and test cycles through its Product:Engagement model. It operates using core models such as 'engagements', 'tests', and 'findings', and is built with Python and Django. Installation is easy, with a setup script that handles dependencies and configuration.

Synopsys Black Duck [\[51\]](#) produces comprehensive security reports that cover vulnerability analysis, license compliance, and risk assessment. The reports provide an overview of all open-source components, highlighting vulnerabilities, outdated components, and license issues. Recommendations for mitigation are included, and the reports are available in various formats such as PDF, HTML, and Excel, allowing for easy sharing and integration with other systems.

Fossa [\[24\]](#) generates detailed reports focused on both security vulnerabilities and license compliance. The reports include information about discovered vulnerabilities, their severity, steps for remediation, and potential legal risks due to license issues. These reports can be exported in formats such as PDF and JSON.

Grype, [\[5\]](#) developed by Anchore, generates vulnerability reports based on the scanned SBOMs. These reports list vulnerabilities with detailed descriptions, severity levels, affected components, and links to additional information such as CVEs. Grype supports output in multiple formats, including JSON, CycloneDX (which can be used as a report), and table format in the CLI. Grype, which conducts vulnerability scanning, works alongside Syft [\[6\]](#), which focuses on generating an SBOM for a container or application. Syft creates the SBOM, which Grype then consumes and runs a security scan to identify vulnerabilities based on the components listed in the SBOM. The resulting security report is produced by Anchore Grype. While Syft and Grype have powerful features as open-source tools, Anchore Enterprise offers a commercial solution with additional capabilities, such as report generation through an advanced User Interface (UI).

Mend (formerly known as WhiteSource), [\[31\]](#) creates in-depth security and compliance reports based on the SBOMs. These reports cover all identified vulnerabilities, risk levels, compliance issues, and recommended fixes, alongside continuous monitoring alerts. The reports can be generated in various formats, suitable for different stakeholders, including HTML, PDF, and Excel.

2.8.2 Test Result Reports of Security and Privacy Assurance Platform

As already mentioned in D2.3, SPHYNX’s Security and Privacy Assurance Platform [50] is a comprehensive framework responsible for monitoring, testing and assessing the security and privacy posture of organizations and their assets in real-time. The reports may include assets, CVE identifiers, descriptions of the vulnerabilities, quality of detection, severity ratings based on CVSS scores, CVSS versions, published libraries and many others (for example Figure 3). Additionally, SPHYNX’s Security and Privacy Assurance Platform provide an advanced UI where all the information can be consulted in interactive dashboards per reports, assets or vulnerabilities.

Assessment ID	Assessment type	Asset ID	Property	Original Severity	Assessed Severity	Initial detection	Last checked	Valid until
xxxxxx	xxxxxx	xxxxx	CONFIDENTIALITY, AVAILABILITY, INTEGRITY	100/100	CRITICAL	xxxx-xx-xx xx:xx:xx	xxxx-xx-xx xx:xx:xx	xxxx-xx-xx xx:xx:xx
Issue: xxxxxx Severity: High QoD(%) : 99 Impact: xxxxxx								

Figure 3: SPHYNX’s Security and Privacy Assurance Platform report

2.8.3 Static Analysis Test Report

Table 2 outlines the desired high-level content of a static analysis test report in the context of RESCALE, generated by a single tool from the RESCALE static code analysis toolbox. In particular the report enables the reader to repeat testing under the original conditions (if possible) due to an extensive description of the testing methods and invocation details. Even though the list of vulnerabilities should cover the main interest into the report, the actual output of the testing tool can be used as backup to understand its processing.

The actual test can be predefined or described using the Environment and Workflow definitions. A trivial example of such a predefined test could be “Execute the tool ‘Dialyzer’ (version 3.2.15) without further options on the Erlang software project using the publicly available Docker container ‘ubuntu:22’ (short SHA1: b0a667f) on an ARM64 based hardware platform”. This approach has a wide range of automation possibilities ranging from plain human readable descriptions (no automation at all) to a fully machine processable descriptions for tools like Ansible [7] or Puppet [45]. The latter approach obviously enables easier reproducibility which is in particular interesting for open source projects.

Further over the last years the Static Analysis Results Interchange Format (SARIF) [35] was developed as an OASIS approved (JSON-based) industry standard without any significant competition. SARIF allows static analysis results to be shared between different tools and platforms in a consistent way. This makes it easier to collect, interpret, and act on the results from multiple analysis tools, while supporting a variety of tools and integration pipelines. By adopting SARIF, RESCALE could benefit from having a unified format for reporting test results.

A more detailed approach to static analysis test reporting will be described in D3.1 as part of the SSCG design and handling.

Table 2: Static Analysis Test Report

Tester	Information about the developer or (sub-)organization responsible for executing the test.
Name/ID	Reference to a predefined static analysis test involving a single tool from the RESCALE static analysis toolbox.
Environment	Hard- and software related environment to ensure transparency and reproducibility.
Workflow	Additional workflow definitions augmenting the referenced test (if necessary) to enhance the reproducibility of the testing.
Output	Plain or processed output of the specific tool including format identifiers.
Vulnerabilities	Includes check with vulnerability databases and respective CVSS score, if possible.
Meta Information	Date of test execution, location data, additional information about the organization, etc.

2.8.4 Dynamic Analysis Test Report

Table 3 presents the high-level content of a dynamic analysis test report within the RESCALE framework, compiled from various modules and tools in the RESCALE dynamic testing module. This report includes information on identified security vulnerabilities in hardware (or firmware) and software components of the supply chain.

Currently, there will be several DSCG reports for different use cases. One report will focus on the inspector, using software/Linux kernel as input and producing a CSV file as output. Another report will cover firmware emulation, where a firmware binary file will serve as input and the output will be a base64-encoded text file. In the future, we will also develop DSCGs for hardware revisions.

A comprehensive explanation of dynamic analysis test reporting will be provided in Deliverable D3.3.

Table 3: Dynamic Analysis Test Report

Tester	Information about the developer or (sub-)organization responsible for executing the test.
Name/ID	Reference to various dynamic analysis tests, including the inspectre tool.
Environment	Hard- and software related environment to ensure transparency and reproducibility.
Workflow	Additional workflow definitions augmenting the referenced test to enhance the reproducibility of the testing.
Output	Plain or processed output of the specific tool including format identifiers.
Vulnerabilities	Includes check with vulnerability databases and respective CVE and CVSS score, if possible.
Meta Information	Date of test execution, location data, additional information about the organization, etc.

2.9 BOM Interoperability

While each BOM specification tries to provide their view on describing components of a product, each one of them started from a specific point of view and expanded from there. Each BOM specification has its own features and capabilities which sometimes they align, but there are some features or information that is missing from the other. Therefore maximum BOM interoperability cannot be guaranteed and tools that exist in the literature and open source communities, while do provide most of the conversion, as will be discussed in 2.9, information will be lost during conversion. Studies, such as [33] and [19] and comparisons between the different BOM specifications, such as [4] showcase these issues in BOM interoperability.

2.9.1 Format Converters

A number of open source tools for format conversion between different BOM specifications, such as CycloneDX and SPDX, exist such as [3], [1] and [2]. However as discussed in 2.9 none of these tools can provide a 100% conversion between the different specification as some specifications have some capabilities and definitions that the others do not, as discussed in Section 2. These tools state explicitly in their web pages that loss of information is expected in either conversion. Specifically, [2] provides a table that showcases a high level overview of the information that will be lost.

3 BOM Format Selection

During the initial stages of the work for developing the TBOM structure, we underwent an extensive search for the most compatible BOM standard to start from and expand or modified according to the needs of the RESCALE project. As a number of BOM standards exist currently, with the three most known being CycloneDX, SPDX and SWID [8] we examined all three to ascertain the most adequate standard.

All three BOM standardized formats are represented by different standardization bodies, SWID[22] published by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) publishes as ISO/IEC 19770-2, SPDX developed by the Linux Foundation and published under ISO/IEC 5962:2021 and CycloneDX developed by OWASP.

3.1 BOM Format Relevant Differences

Each BOM standard format was initially developed with different intended purposes, thus the current versions reflect their initial premise. For example; SPDX, being the oldest of these TBOM formats, was largely intended for open source licensing use cases. Although eventually all formats exceeded their initial use cases and extended into additional ones, however their initial purpose shaped and guides their evolution.

The following list contains a summary of the main differences of the main three BOM standardization format with regards to the project.

- SWID has no JSON support, whereas SPDX and CycloneDX do.
- Use of JSON supports BOM interoperability between SPDX and CycloneDX.
- All three BOM standard formats are standardized by reputable bodies:
 - SWID: ISO/IEC 19770-2.
 - SPDX: ISO/IEC 5962:2021.
 - CycloneDX: OWASP.
- SPDX possesses less support from HBOM from our findings.
- CycloneDX has robust support for HBOM from our findings.
- CycloneDX has very extensive documentation and a well-organized website with visual aids.
 - Assists in better understanding the schema faster.
- An Erlang generator to create CycloneDX TBOMs exists, which is very useful to partner and use-case provider PST.
 - The developer of this Erlang generator is a contact of PST.
 - PST have a pull-request in tool repo for JSON support, bug fixes, etc.

- Link to tool: https://github.com/voltone/rebar3_sbom

CycloneDX, as an OWASP project, is aligned much more closely with cybersecurity use cases, containing capabilities such as Bill of Vulnerabilities (BOV)s, Vulnerability Disclosure Report and CycloneDX Attestations which are related to the RESCALE Project goals.

Based on the above observations the consortium's consensus was largely in favour of CycloneDX. With no strong objections to this decision, CycloneDX was chosen as the BOM format to implement the TBOM. In the following subsection, 3.2, a detailed analysis of SPDX and CycloneDX is offered in order to further justify this choice in BOM format.

3.2 SPDX & CycloneDX BOM Format Detailed Analysis

Both SPDX and CDX are widely recognised standards for SBOM formats, with differing strong suits and weaknesses. A detailed comparison of these formats follows to explain how the decision in BOM format was informed.

3.2.1 SPDX

SPDX is an open standard for communicating information about software components, including licenses, copyrights, and security data. It is widely used in industry and has a large community of adopters. Some of the key advantages of SPDX include the following: SPDX is a mature standard that has been around for over a decade, with a well-established community and a wide range of tools and libraries available, SPDX is widely adopted in the industry, with many companies and organizations using it to manage their software components, SPDX also supports a wide range of formats, including JSON, XML, and RDF, making it easy to integrate with different systems and tools.

There are, however, also some disadvantages with SPDX: SPDX has a complex data model, which can make it difficult to understand and use, especially for those without prior experience with the standard; also SPDX is primarily focused on software components, and its support for hardware components is limited.

3.2.2 CycloneDX

CycloneDX is a lightweight SBOM format that is designed to be easy to use and understand. It is gaining popularity in the industry, particularly among companies that require managing complex software supply chains. Some of the key advantages of CycloneDX include: having a simple and intuitive data model, making it easy to understand and use, even for those without prior experience with the standard, built-in support for hardware components, and support for a wide range of formats, including JSON and XML, facilitating interoperability.

CycloneDX also carries several disadvantages: it is a relatively new standard, and its community and ecosystem are still developing, also it is not yet as widely adopted as SPDX, which can

make it harder to find tools and libraries that support the standard when compared to SPDX.

3.2.3 SPDX & CycloneDX Comparison

The following table summarises pertinent key differences between SPDX and CDX:

Characteristic	SPDX	CycloneDX
Maturity	Mature	Relatively New
Adoption	Widely Adopted	Less Widely Adopted
Complexity	Complex	Simple
Hardware Component Support	Limited	Inherent
Flexibility	Multiple Format Support	Multiple Format Support
Community	Large Community	Developing Community

In conclusion, the choice between SPDX and CycloneDX formats is dependent on the specific requirements of the RESCALE project. SPDX is an appropriate choice for companies needing to manage complex software supply chains with large communities of adopters, whereas CycloneDX is a good choice for companies that need to manage both software and hardware components with a simple and intuitive data model, which was pertinent given the hardware dimension of RESCALE.

4 Trusted Bill of Materials Structure

This section defines the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) structure. The specification is explained through the subsections herein. In the TBOM structure diagram shown in Figure 4 an overview of the TBOM, it's relationships and its fields is presented. More detail is given in the JSON code in the Annex, section 9.1. Note that the hash codes in this program had to be split across two lines as to fit on-page.

4.1 Overview TBOM Sections

The TBOM structure contains all the necessary information required to provide a level of Trust Assurance on products used in a supply chain. Figure 4 provides a high level overview of the all the various fields of the TBOM specification along with several of the externally referenced documents.

Figure 4: TBOM Structure

The fields of Figure 4 are:

- **ID**: This field contains a unique identifier, such as a UUID or URN, to enable explicit

referencing of each TBOM.

- **SBOM:** The SBOM field is a reference to an existing SBOM from which the TBOM will be generated, which consists of a link, such as a URL or local path, to this document along with a hash value for integrity.
- **Vulnerabilities Reference:** This field is a link to an external document holding vulnerability information about the component which the TBOM describes. This will be implemented as a Bill of Vulnerabilities (BOV). This document is continuously updated, and can only be referenced externally. The hash of the document, as such, cannot be included in the TBOM due to continuous updates which would make the hash constantly redundant, and require regeneration of the TBOM.
- **SSCG:** The SSCG field includes a link to the SSCG report, as well as a hash of the report for integrity purposes.
- **DSCG:** The DSCG contains a link to the DSCG report along with a hash of the document for integrity verification.
- **Trust Assurance:** The information which can be used to verify integrity of any externally referenced resources is compiled in this field, for example aggregation of hashes into one code for quick verification, and the storing of TBOM signatures.
- **Testing Proof:** This section has a twofold purpose, it can hold cryptographic outputs such as hashes or signatures which offer proof that testing occurred as stated, and the second purpose of the section is to store links to external documents, for example to trace logs as part of attestation. CycloneDX types such as hash, evidence and attestation are usable in this field.
- **Extensions:** This section exists to leave room for modifications and enlargement of the TBOM should it become necessary at a later point in the project.

4.2 Detailed Specification

This section will provide a detailed explanation of each of the TBOM sections shown in Figure 4. Code excerpts from Section 9 Annex I 9.1 and Annex II 9.2 will be included for each of these TBOM sections along with descriptions of types, fields, usage and potential modifications as the RESCALE project advances. Where the usage of the field in the RESCALE project is non-standard, or is under consideration for modification this will be explained. Additionally, where a field has already been described in a prior section it will be included under a "described prior" point. The same field with differing usage to an earlier description will be described again in that context. The types and fields contained in the following JSON examples are from the CycloneDX 1.6 JSON specification [16].

4.2.1 TBOM ID & Header

The code excerpt in Figure 5 showcases the beginning part of a CycloneDX document, which we will refer to as the document "header". This header specifies several parameters regarding format and schema, the usage of which will be explained presently.

```
"serialNumber": "urn:uuid:856440af-7181-4293-b1f1-aade5c738a74",  
  "version": 1,  
  "$schema": "http://cyclonedx.org/schema/bom-1.6.schema.json",  
  "bomFormat": "CycloneDX",  
  "specVersion": "1.6",  
  "components":
```

Figure 5: TBOM Header CycloneDX JSON Example

- **Serial Number:** This is a unique identifier for the BOM document. The identifier must conform to the RFC-4122 standard for universal unique identifiers.
- **Version (BOM):** This field contains the version information for this specific BOM. Specifically, it holds an integer which should be incremented whenever a change is made to the BOM.
- **Schema:** the format, or language, which the BOM is written in. For the TBOM implementation we have selected JSON, however other options such as XML are available.
- **BOM Format:** this field specifies the standard format which this BOM uses, in this case it is CycloneDX.
- **Spec Version:** this field contains the specification version of the chosen BOM format, in this case 1.6 is specified, denoting that version 1.6 of CycloneDX is used.
- **Components:** This field denotes the inventory of components in the BOM, in this case these are the SBOM, SSCG, DSCG, vulnerability document, trust assurance, testing proof and extensions sections of the BOM which will be described shortly, with the respective files being the components themselves.

4.2.2 SBOM

The code excerpt in Figure 6 illustrates the SBOM section of the TBOM document. It is important to note that this excerpt shows an link to an SBOM document, but this SBOM could also be entirely subsumed into the TBOM and included in-line in the JSON. The TBOM generation process will use an SBOM as input, and the TBOM can effectively be described as a modified SBOM for the inclusion of parameters to hold outputs from RESCALE security testing, continuous vulnerability detection, trust assurance and testing proof. For this deliverable the SBOM section is implemented as an external reference for the reason of creating a readable TBOM document, which does not have significant volumes of SBOM JSON contained within.

```

"bom-ref": "sbom1-ref",
"description": "SBOM for this TBOM",
"externalReferences": [
  {
    "comment": "SBOM URL",
    "type": "distribution",
    "url": "https://rescale/sbom1/",
    "hashes": [
      {
        "alg": "SHA-256",
        "content": "c0fcf1d55386a4f260c46a0947
e24411a496646e69395dd84567c90fe043b957"
      }
    ]
  }
]
"name": "SBOM1",
"purl": "pkg:package/link",
"type": "file",
"version": "1"

```

Figure 6: SBOM Link CycloneDX JSON Example

- **BOM-Ref:** a unique identifier which can be used to reference this element in the BOM, an example of a technology used for this is the UUID. One restriction is that the BOM-ref must not use URN format, so as not to conflict with BOM-Links to external BOMs. The BOM-Ref can be placed on many elements of BOMs and essentially can act as a label to enable referring to these elements.
- **Description:** stores a short textual description about this BOM component.
- **External References:** points to an object or resource outside of this BOM element. In this case the SBOM from which this TBOM was generated.

Comment (External Reference): text to provide additional information about the external reference.

Type (External Reference): the type of external reference, in this case it is of type: distribution. This type denotes a download location. The external references type, per the CycloneDX 1.6 JSON specification must be listed as one of the following: *vcs, issue-tracker, website, advisories, bom, mailing-list, social, chat, documentation, support, source-distribution, distribution, distribution-lake, license, build-meta, build-system, release-notes, security-contact, model-card, log, configuration, evidence, formulation, attestation, threat-model, adversary-model, risk-assessment, vulnerability-assertion, exploitability-statement, pentest-report, static-analysis-report, dynamic-analysis-report, runtime-analysis-report, component-analysis-report, maturity-report, certification-report, codified-infrastructure, quality-metrics, Plans of Action and Milestones, electronic-signature, digital-signature, rfc-9116, other.*

URL: link to the download location for the SBOM used to generate this TBOM. When formatted as a URN this can be used to link to another BOM.

- **Hashes:** cryptographic hash, or multiple hashes, of the external document. In this case it will store the hash of the SBOM used to generate this TBOM.
 - Alg:** the algorithm used to generate the hash, SHA-256 for this specific example. Both SHA and Blake hashings algorithms with various hash sizes.
 - Content:** The hash value. This must be a properly formatted hash, in terms of the length of the CycloneDX hash content field corresponding to the stated hash length of the hashing algorithm.
- **Name:** the component name, in this example it is "SBOM1".
- **PURL:** Identity / link for component which uses package-URL. It must conform to the Package URL PURL specification [46]. In this case the package-URL would point to the SBOM used to generate this TBOM. Package URL is generally used to target software packages, such as those one might download and install. This is similar to, but not to be confused with, the URL field which can link to essentially any external asset
- **Type (Component):** the type of component, in this case it is type: file. The file in question is the SBOM which was used to generate this TBOM. Other types include: Application, Framework, Library, Container, Platform, Operating-System, Device, device-driver, firmware, file, machine-learning-model, data or cryptographic asset.
- **Version:** the version number of the component, in this case the SBOM. CycloneDX requests this to comply with semantic versioning, but it is not enforced.

4.2.3 Metadata

With the SBOM being included to the TBOM as an external reference, several CycloneDX fields which one may expect to see in the TBOM are not present, such as those in the Metadata category, like authors, tools and manufacturers. This is because that information is already included in the SBOM which we link to, and would be included directly in the TBOM if the approach of copying the SBOM text directly into the document was taken. The Metadata category, and its fields, are also used for expressing the tool with which the BOM was created and license information, which is of interest from the perspective of storing useful information about the generation of the TBOM generation process.

Including the SBOM text directly in the TBOM, with its own metadata fields, would complicate adding the same to describe the TBOM itself, and it is noteworthy that these two documents will not have been generated at the same time. As such a generic example excerpt has been prepared in Figure 7 as a best estimate, and included as a separate annex element in Section 9, Annex II 9.2.

```
"metadata": {
  "component": {
    "bom-ref": "tbom1-metadata",
    "name": "tbom1/metadata",
    "type": "file"
  },
  "supplier": {
    "name": "rescale-project"
  },
  "timestamp": "2024-09-24T13:20:53.367071+00:00",
  "tools": [
    {
      "name": "tbomgenerator",
      "vendor": "rescale-consortium."
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 7: TBOM Metadata CycloneDX JSON Example

- **Metadata:** Additional information about this bill of materials BOM.

Component (Metadata): The component name which the BOM describes.

BOM-Ref: a unique identifier which can be used to reference this element in the BOM.

Name (Component): The name sub-type of the CycloneDX "Component" field, in "Metadata" contains the name of the component being described.

Type (Component): The component type, which must be one of the following CycloneDX 1.6 schema values: *Application, Framework, Library, Container, Platform, Operating-System, Device, device-driver, firmware, file, machine-learning-model, data or cryptographic asset.*

- **Supplier:** the organization which supplied the component which this Bill of Materials (BOM) describes.

Name (Supplier): the supplier name.

- **Timestamp:** the time and date of BOM generation.

- **Tools:** the tools used to create, validate, or enrich the BOM.

Name: the name of the tool.

Vendor: the vendor of the tool.

4.2.4 Vulnerabilities Reference

This section of the TBOM refers to the external document which stores the vulnerabilities regarding the software or hardware component that this TBOM represents. This document will be generated by tools such as described in Figure 3 earlier in this document. For the

vulnerabilities reference there is no hash section as the referenced document will continuously be updated with new findings. Since a TBOM is a static document due to its nature, updating the vulnerability reference hash would also incur the additional task of adding a new entry to the blockchain or ledger which provides the immutable trust to this TBOM. Instead, the vulnerability document will contain a hash value of the TBOM.

Regarding the integrity of the vulnerability document itself, the component and processes to generate this document for use within RESCALE are still under development and integration, meaning that a concrete solution to the integrity of the outputs does not yet exist. One promising solution is the placement of links and hash values of both the TBOM and its respective vulnerability document in the same blockchain, or ledger entry, thereby immutably linking them together. The issue of generating a new ledger entry upon the discovery of vulnerabilities could be mitigated by generating new ledger entries for batches of updates, with the immediacy of the update being directly related to the severity of the discovered vulnerability. For example a severe vulnerability could always trigger an instant update. More general solutions, such as an alternative method of verifying the integrity of the vulnerability document, are also under consideration.

```
"bom-ref": "bov1-ref",
"description": "Continuously updated Bill of Vulnerabilities",
"externalReferences": [
  {
    "comment": "Link to BOV",
    "type": "distribution",
    "url": "https://rescale/bov1/"
  }
],
"name": "BOV1",
"purl": "pkg:package/link",
"type": "file",
"version": "1"
```

Figure 8: Vulnerabilities Document Link CycloneDX JSON Example

- **BOM-Ref:** The CycloneDX BOM-Ref unique identifier for the continuously updated vulnerabilities document which this TBOM links to. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Description:** The text description of this bill of vulnerabilities element of the TBOM. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **External References:** The external references field in this case contains the types to link to the external document containing vulnerabilities.

Comment: Provides additional information about the bill of vulnerabilities external reference.

Type (External References): An external reference of type distribution, denoting a download location for the vulnerabilities document. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

URL (External References): The link to retrieve the bill of vulnerabilities document.

- **Name:** The component name, in this case "BOV1".
- **PURL:** The package URL associated with the vulnerabilities document. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Type (Component):** The vulnerability document component type is File. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Version:** The version number of this bill of vulnerabilities component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

4.2.5 SSCG

This section holds the link to the results report of the SSCG shown in Figure 9, which deals with static testing of the respective component's code-base. A link to this report is included along with a hash value for integrity purposes. The report could be included directly in the TBOM, however this piece of the RESCALE project is still under development and as such adding it as an external reference allows the TBOM structure to be developed without having a dependency on the exact content of these security testing reports.

```
"bom-ref": "sscg1-ref",
"description": "Static test report",
"externalReferences": [
  {
    "comment": "SSCG link",
    "type": "static-analysis-report",
    "url": "https://rescale/sscg1/",
    "hashes": [
      {
        "alg": "SHA-256",
        "content": "64ec88ca00b268e5ba1a35678a
1b5316d212f4f366b2477232534a8aeca37f3c"
      }
    ]
  }
]
"name": "SSCG1",
"purl": "pkg:package/link",
"type": "file"
```

Figure 9: SSCG Document Link CycloneDX JSON Example

- **BOM-Ref:** The BOM-Ref which acts as a unique identifier for this TBOM component representing the SSCG static test report. Detailed type description in 4.2.2.
- **Description:** The text description associated with this TBOM component.

- **External References:** The external references field contains the types to reference the SSCG document. Detailed type description in 4.2.2.

Comment (External References): A text comment to provide additional information regarding the external reference to the SSCG.

Type (External References): this External References Type is: static-analysis-report. This refers to either a machine-readable, or human-readable report on a static code analysis. The intention of this CycloneDX static-analysis-report type, per the explanation provided by the CycloneDX 1.6 JSON specification is: "SARIF or proprietary machine or human-readable report for which static analysis has identified code quality, security, and other potential issues with the source code." [16]. While currently fit for purpose, there is potential to modify the underlying CycloneDX schema here, in particular, to better align this type with the RESCALE project's concept of the SSCG, including bespoke elements and innovations which arise from that tooling.

URL: stores the link to retrieve the SSCG document

- **Hashes:** used to store the hash of the SSCG document

Alg: The algorithm used to generate the hash of the SSCG document, namely SHA-256.

Content: This field holds the hash value, which was generated by hashing the SSCG document.

- **Name:** The component name, which is "SSCG1" in this case.
- **PURL:** The package URL associated with this SSCG component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Type (Component):** The SSCG component type is of type File. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Version:** The version number of this component which represents the SSCG. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

4.2.6 DSCG

This section of the TBOM includes a link to the dynamic testing report (the DSCG) of the component executable, along with a hash of this report for integrity. This section of the document mirrors the previous one dealing with the SSCG, as the DSCG could also be included in the TBOM directly, however the tools to produce this document are still under development. For these same reasons, this section also uses an external reference. The scoping of modifications to the CycloneDX schema is likely to be beneficial upon the completion of the DSCG tools.

```
"bom-ref": "dscg1-ref",
"description": "Dynamic test report",
"externalReferences": [
  {
    "comment": "DSCG link",
    "type": "dynamic-analysis-report",
    "url": "https://rescale/dscg1"
    "hashes": [
      {
        "alg": "SHA-256",
        "content": "4bac0ad744f0bdc9e4dc7cb323
96f1d4a0eae254981b1f34e2a36b1e4170681c"
      }
    ]
  }
]
"name": "DSCG1",
"purl": "pkg:package/link",
"type": "file"
```

Figure 10: DSCG Document Link CycloneDX JSON Example

- **BOM-Ref:** The BOM-Ref unique identifier for this TBOM component representing the DSCG. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Description:** Textual description for additional information about this DSCG component.
- **External References:** This holds the fields which provide details to access the external reference, which is the DSCG document in this case. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

Comment: Text that add additional details about this external reference.

Type (External Reference): the CycloneDX 1.6 type used here is the "dynamic-analysis-report". Per the CycloneDX 1.6 specification this is a "Dynamic analysis report that has identified issues such as vulnerabilities and misconfigurations" [16]. As with the SSCG, the RESCALE DSCG report can be serviced by the current CycloneDX 1.6 specification, but modifications to this type (or perhaps the addition of a new type) would make for a better-aligned solution.

URL: stores the link to retrieve the DSCG document. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

- **Hashes:** Used to store the hash of the DSCG document. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

Alg: The type of algorithm used to generate the hash of the DSCG document, SHA-5 is used here. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

Content: The hash value which was produced by hashing the DSCG document. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

- **Name:** The name of this TBOM component. In this case it is "DSCG1".

- **PURL:** The package URL associated with this DSCG component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Type (Component)** The DSCG component is of type File. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

4.2.7 Trust Assurance

The trust assurance element of the TBOM document, shown in Figure 11, is intended to store cryptographic assets which can be used to verify the integrity of the TBOM and the other documents which comprise it. The specific intended purpose is to address marking the ledger entry, or block, of the previous version of the **TBOM** which this **TBOM** obsoletes, and storing the hash of that entry. In this way one can follow a chain specific to a certain **TBOM** which is constructed by the inclusion of the previous TBOM version's hash in the new version. The link to this previous entry, or alternately a unique identifier, is needed in this section also.

```
"bom-ref": "trustAssurance1",
"description": "Combined hash for linked files, hash of previous block",
"name": "TrustAssurance",
"purl": "pkg:package/link",
"type": "cryptographic-asset",
"hashes": [
  {
    "alg": "SHA-256",
    "content": "c8ceb5bb5b8bb75e64286541c1
d2014b8600de29da6ca79b7464c0183f9906b6"
  }
]
```

Figure 11: TBOM Trust Assurance CycloneDX JSON Example

- **BOM-Ref:** This BOM-Ref field contains the unique identifier for this Trust Assurance TBOM component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Description:** Textual description for adding details about this Trust Assurance component.
- **Name:** The name of the Trust Assurance TBOM component. In this case it is "trustAssurance1".
- **PURL:** this package URL is intended to address the ledger entry, or blockchain block, of the previous version of this TBOM - which is obsoleted by this instance. This PURL could also reasonably be replaced by a URL field.
- **Type (Component):** the type of component, in this instance, is a cryptographic-asset. This is a set of hash values of the various documents comprising the TBOM. These could reasonably be replaced by another type of cryptographic asset for assuring trust, such as signatures. The hash of the previous ledger entry is also required to be included as an

entry. The other types permitted in the CycloneDX schema are; *algorithms, protocols, certificates, keys, tokens, and secret*

- **Hashes:** Used to store the hashes generated by the RESCALE trust assurance mechanisms. This item could reasonably be changed to accommodate other types of cryptographic assets or evidence. This example shows that hash value can be stored in the "hashes" type, describing outputs of the RESCALE Trust Assurance component, and specifically providing cryptographic proof. These hashes can be numerous - to allow for different sizes or algorithms, but are intended to all describe the same component. RESCALE proposes modifying this to allow components such as the RESCALE Trust Assurance component, which could present multi-faceted outputs, to store several hashes describing several different outputs in one CycloneDX "hashes". In the present CycloneDX 1.6 implementation of this part of the specification these would have to be differentiated by specifying the information in a comment or description field. With modifications to the schema this can be made into a more elegant solution.

Alg: Denotes the type of hashing algorithm used, SHA-256 in this case. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

Content: This hash content type is used to store a blockchain block's hash (or alternatively, of a ledger element) which represents the previous TBOM version - which this version makes obsolete. It is important to specify that the block for the TBOM currently being generated would not yet exist, and this hash is of the block representing its predecessor. The initial version of a TBOM will not have to conform to this and can simply load a hash of itself into the field. The blockchain, or ledger, referred to here is the RESCALE Trusted Storage.

4.2.8 Testing Proof

This TBOM section stores proof that testing occurred. The mechanisms to prove that security testing on a component, such as with the SSCG and DSCG tools, were conducted in a tamper-free and valid way. The importance of this is that it directly impacts the trustworthiness of the reports produced by these tests. Mechanisms such as zero-knowledge proofs and remote attestation are under examination as solutions to this, and these are discussed in more detail in section 7.4. The outputs of such validation mechanisms must be stored in the TBOM.

```

"bom-ref": "testingProof1",
"description": "Combined hash, signature for linked files",
"name": "TestingProof",
"purl": "pkg:package/link",
"type": "cryptographic-asset",
"externalReferences": [
  {
    "comment": "Test proof link",
    "type": "distribution",
    "url": "https://rescale/testingProof1/",
    "hashes": [
      {
        "alg": "SHA-256",
        "content": "745e945081cc16d23aa371859e
6c8697fbbb4dabdc4164f6f4f2d0c806a52d3"
      }
    ]
  }
]

```

Figure 12: TBOM Testing Proof CycloneDX JSON Example

- **BOM-Ref:** The unique identifier for this Testing Proof component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Description:** A textual field to add details about this testing proof component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Name:** The name of this Testing Proof component.
- **PURL:** The package URL associated with this Testing Proof component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Type (component):** the type of component is a cryptographic-asset. In this field the hash code which can be used to verify proof of testing is stored. This could reasonably be interchanged with another type of cryptographic asset such as a signature, or evidence.
- **External References:** The same usage as in 4.2.2.

Type (External References): The same usage as in 4.2.2.

URL (External References): The link to access the testing proof document is stored here, this document can provide more robust information such as logs regarding the testing

- **Hashes:** the hash code providing proof of testing, which could be interchanged with another cryptographic asset depending on the output of the selected testing proof tool(s). As mentioned previously, the present implementation of the "Hashes" type in CycloneDX could be modified (or perhaps a similar type, serving a distinct function) could be implemented to provide a more elegant solution for tools or tests which output several cryptographic assets.

Alg: The algorithm used to generate the hash value, in this case SHA-256. Detailed field description in 4.2.2. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

Content: The hash value generated by the RESCALE testing proof. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

4.2.9 Extensions

The extensions section is included to cater to modifications and additions which will potentially arise as the RESCALE project advances, as a result of unforeseen requirements and increased knowledge gained through the platform implementation and execution of minimum viable products. As such, this section can presently be seen as a placeholder for future work. The CycloneDX model describes extensions as fast prototyping of new capabilities and support for specialized and future use cases, and also notes that the project encourages development of extensions that target specialized or industry-specific use cases [17].

[H]

```
"bom-ref": "extension-ref",
"description": "Placeholder for future modification or extension",
"externalReferences": [
  {
    "comment": "extension",
    "type": "distribution",
    "url": "https://rescale/extension/"
  }
]
"name": "extension",
"purl": "pkg:package/link",
"type": "data",
"version": "1"
```

- **BOM-Ref:** The BOM-Ref uniquely identifying this extensions component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Description:** The description field for adding information about this extensions component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **External References:** The same usage as in 4.2.2.

Comment: A field to add additional detail about this external reference. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

Type (External References): The same usage as in 4.2.2.

URL: The URL associated with this extensions component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

- **Name:** The name of this extensions component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

- **PURL:** The package URL associated with this extensions component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.
- **Type:** the Component type "data" is assigned here, and the use of the term is defined in the CycloneDX 1.6 JSON schema as "A collection of discrete values that convey information" [16].
- **Version:** The version number of this extensions component. Detailed field description in 4.2.2.

4.3 Dependencies and External Entities

The TBOM has several dependencies, which are better described as components that comprise the TBOM. These are external documents, the content of which could alternatively be included directly in the TBOM, however several of these external documents are not yet developed due to having deadlines later than this D4.1 TBOM structure deliverable, and as such referencing them externally was appropriate and allowed a cohesive TBOM to be produced. These include the SBOM instance on which the TBOM instance is based, static security testing report (SSCG), dynamic security testing report (DSCG), the continuously updated vulnerabilities document and the proof that testing was conducted correctly.

These dependency documents, the DSCG and SSCG, can be represented using existing types in CycloneDX, static and dynamic test report types. The trust assurance and testing proof can also operate using existing CycloneDX types. Furnishing the CycloneDX libraries with the update and new types to better accommodate the intention of the TBOM would, in many cases, make for a more elegant implementation of this specification. Given that, at the time of release of D4.1, the dependencies for the TBOM do not yet exist, the outputs of these tools will be required to follow the specification outlined herein. It was determined premature to attempt to extend the CycloneDX libraries with bespoke types alongside the specification definition, and preferable to execute this work during implementation phases in WP4 and WP5.

4.4 BOM Format

The TBOM is implemented in CycloneDX 1.6, in JSON format. Implementation in this format and language enables the option of interoperability with the SPDX BOM format, with the limitations as discussed in Section 2.9, and presents this option for future consideration. Implementing the BOM in BOM specification in a neutral standard was also examined. This would act as a detailed blueprint agnostic of BOM formats or languages, which would aim to impart knowledge of how to implement the TBOM in any format or schema, however this would have lowered the usability of the D4.1 output for developing the minimum viable product (MVP). This neutral schema is under consideration for inclusion in future work.

5 TBOM Lifecycle

This section details the lifecycle of a TBOM from its conception to its deprecation as well as the states which it can exist in, as well as the transition between those states. Figure 13 depicts all the possible TBOM Lifecycle states each of which will be described more analytically in subsection 5.1.

It must be noted that each TBOM is relevant for a specific product version. Other versions of a product require different TBOMs. If for some reason, additional testing is either required or requested for a specific product that already has a TBOM, then the results of the additional tests are used in conjunction with the previous results to generate a new TBOM, for the same product version, deprecating the old one.

Figure 13: TBOM Lifecycle

It should be noted that While the SSCG generation and DSCG generation are not per se part of the TBOM Lifecycle, as the TBOM begins its existence during the TBOM generation, these two states are an integral and important part of the TBOM lifecycle.

After the SSCG and DSCG have been generated as part of the initial two states, the TBOM is being generated. Once the TBOM has been generated then the validation phase is initiated. This is the only phase at which the TBOM can become invalidated and deleted as, once it has been validated and published into the blockchain, being an append-only ledger, it can never be deleted.

Depending on whether a vulnerability has been detected and the severity of that vulnerability the TBOM will shift into a specific severity state. The TBOM can only go from a lower vulnerability to a higher vulnerability state since the TBOM is valid for a specific product version. If newer versions are developed then a new TBOM must be created. Therefore as new vulnerabilities are found it is possible that higher states of vulnerability will occur for the product.

Finally, if, for the same product version, new assessments are made, a new TBOM is generated and deprecates the current one, and therefore the TBOM will be moved to the deprecated state where it will be considered obsolete.

5.1 TBOM Lifecycle States

This section describes the different state in which a TBOM can exist. This information is not stored in the TBOM itself, rather it pertains to the lifecycle of the TBOM as it moves through different stages and occurrences on the RESCALE platform, including being replaced by a newer version of the TBOM or new vulnerabilities being discovered.

5.1.1 SSCG generation

This is the first step towards the generation of the TBOM. During this state, the TBOM does not exist or is being generated, and therefore cannot be considered part of the TBOM lifecycle. However in this state, all the static analysis tools will be deployed in order to generate the SSCG, an integral part of the TBOM itself. This state is finished when the SSCG is generated by the SSCG generator and moves to the DSCG generation state.

5.1.2 DSCG generation

Similar to the SSCG generation state, the TBOM still does not exist or is being generated. However as the DSCG is similarly a critical component of the TBOM. However in this state, all the dynamic analysis tools will be deployed in order to generate the DSCG. The DSCG generation is finished when the DSCG is generated by the DSCG generator and moves to the TBOM generation state.

5.1.3 TBOM generation

The TBOM generation state is the first state of the TBOM lifecycle. During this state the TBOM will be generated by combining the SBOM, the SSCG and the DSCG. Once the TBOM generator is invoked and the TBOM is generated the TBOM goes to the next state.

5.1.4 TBOM validation

The TBOM validation state is initiated upon the generation of the TBOM. The TBOM is checked for validity, by the TBOM validator, both syntactically and cryptographically. If any of the validation process fails, then the TBOM is considered invalid and is promptly moved to the invalid state. If the validation process succeeds then the TBOM is valid and can be published on the blockchain. Once the TBOM is published then the TBOM is moved to the the active state.

5.1.5 TBOM invalid

If the TBOM reaches the TBOM invalid state then the TBOM is considered unusable and is promptly deleted.

5.1.6 TBOM active

Once the TBOM is published, then the TBOM is considered active and usable. So long as no vulnerabilities were found and during that the TBOM is active the Security Assurance does not detect any vulnerabilities, the TBOM state remains active. If a vulnerability is found at any moment then the TBOM state will change depending on the severity. The calculation of the severity could be done with calculators such as [34].

The next state is depended upon the severity found. If there is at least a critical vulnerability found, then the TBOM will transition to the Critical Vulnerability state. If no critical vulnerability is found, but there is at least one High vulnerability, then the TBOM will transition to the High Vulnerability state. If no Critical or High vulnerability is found, but there is at least one Medium Vulnerability, then the TBOM will transition to the Medium Vulnerability state. If no Critical, High or Medium vulnerability is found, but there is at least one Low Vulnerability, then the TBOM will transition to the Low Vulnerability state.

Finally, if a new TBOM is published for the same product, with no changes in the source code, then this TBOM will transition to the TBOM deprecated state and will no longer be usable or active.

5.1.7 Low Vulnerability

In the Low Vulnerability state, the TBOM is still active but at least one Low Vulnerability is found and no Medium, High and Critical Vulnerability is found. The TBOM state will remain the same, unless a new Vulnerability is found, and then the TBOM will transition to the relevant Vulnerability state similar to the discussion in the active state. Finally if a new TBOM is published, the TBOM will transition to the TBOM deprecated state.

5.1.8 Medium Vulnerability

In the Medium Vulnerability state, the TBOM is still active but at least one Medium Vulnerability is found and no High and Critical Vulnerability is found. The TBOM state will remain the same, unless a new Vulnerability is found, and then the TBOM will transition to the relevant Vulnerability state similar to the discussion in the active state. Finally if a new TBOM is published, the TBOM will transition to the TBOM deprecated state.

5.1.9 High Vulnerability

In the High Vulnerability state, the TBOM is still active but at least one High Vulnerability is found and no Critical Vulnerability is found. The TBOM state will remain the same, unless a new Vulnerability is found, and then the TBOM will transition to the relevant Vulnerability state similar to the discussion in the active state. Finally if a new TBOM is published, the TBOM will transition to the TBOM deprecated state.

5.1.10 Critical Vulnerability

In the Critical Vulnerability state, the TBOM is still active but at least one Critical Vulnerability is found. The TBOM state cannot change as no more severe vulnerability rating can be found. Finally if a new TBOM is published, the TBOM will transition to the TBOM deprecated state.

5.1.11 TBOM deprecated

The TBOM will enter this state when a new TBOM is published. While the TBOM cannot be deleted, it is considered deprecated and not active any more. The new TBOM will contain the current TBOM results as well as the new assessment results.

6 TBOM Distribution Mechanism

The secure and efficient distribution of TBOMs is a critical component of modern supply chain management. TBOMs provide a comprehensive, verifiable record of the components, processes and parties involved in the creation and distribution of a product. Effective distribution mechanisms for TBOMs are essential for ensuring data integrity, preventing tampering and enabling seamless data sharing across various stakeholders in a supply chain.

6.1 Types of TBOM Distribution Mechanisms

TBOM distribution can be broadly categorized into **on-ledger** and **off-ledger** mechanisms. Each approach offers unique advantages and challenges, making them suitable for different scenarios depending on factors such as cost, scalability, privacy, and regulatory compliance. In this section, we explore both on-ledger and off-ledger distribution methods, examining their respective benefits and limitations, and discuss hybrid approaches that combine elements of both to optimize TBOM management.

6.1.1 On-Ledger TBOM Distribution

On-ledger distribution involves storing TBOMs directly on a blockchain or distributed ledger. This approach leverages the core properties of blockchain technology — decentralization, immutability, transparency, and security — to enhance the integrity and traceability of supply chain data. When a TBOM is stored on a blockchain, every addition, update, or modification is recorded as a new transaction, creating a permanent, tamper-proof audit trail.

The advantages of on-ledger TBOM distribution are primarily centered around leveraging blockchain's inherent features such as immutability, transparency, decentralization, and automation to enhance trust, security, and operational efficiency in supply chains. Some of these advantages include:

- *Immutability and Trust:* Blockchain's immutable ledger ensures that once a TBOM is recorded, it cannot be altered or tampered with, providing a high level of trust and integrity.
- *Transparency and Accountability:* Public blockchains offer full transparency, allowing all participants in the network to verify the authenticity and history of the TBOM.
- *Decentralization and Security:* Removes the need for a centralized authority, reducing the risk of a single point of failure or control.
- *Automated Operations through Smart Contracts:* Smart contracts can automate the creation, distribution, and validation of TBOMs, reducing manual effort and human error.

However, there are challenges associated with on-ledger TBOM distribution that organizations must consider when implementing this method. These challenges typically revolve around scal-

ability, costs, privacy, and compliance concerns that can impact the feasibility of blockchain-based solutions for TBOM management. Key challenges include:

- *Scalability and Performance Issues:* Storing large TBOMs directly on-chain can lead to network congestion and slow processing times, especially on public blockchains.
- *High Transaction Costs:* Blockchain networks, such as Ethereum, may incur high transaction fees for data storage and processing, making on-ledger solutions expensive for frequent or large-scale TBOM updates.
- *Privacy Concerns:* While blockchains provide transparency, they can also expose sensitive information. Data privacy must be carefully managed through encryption, zero-knowledge proofs, or selective disclosure methods.
- *Regulatory Compliance:* Storing sensitive data on public ledgers may conflict with data protection regulations like GDPR. Organizations must navigate these legal complexities to avoid penalties.

6.1.2 Off-Ledger TBOM Distribution

Off-ledger distribution involves managing and storing TBOMs entirely outside of the blockchain network, using traditional centralized or decentralized storage systems while utilizing the blockchain only for integrity verification or as a pointer to data locations. This approach is distinct in that it keeps TBOM data completely off the blockchain, offering advantages in cost reduction, flexibility, and speed, especially for environments where frequent updates and privacy are paramount.

The advantages of off-ledger TBOM distribution stem from its flexibility, cost-efficiency, scalability, and privacy control, allowing organizations to manage TBOMs in a way that aligns with their specific operational needs and constraints. Key advantages include:

- *Cost Efficiency:* Off-ledger storage avoids the high transaction fees associated with blockchain networks, making it more suitable for organizations managing large volumes of TBOMs or frequent updates.
- *Scalability and Speed:* Centralized databases or decentralized storage solutions like IPFS, Filecoin or Storj can handle large datasets more efficiently, providing faster read/write access compared to on-chain storage.
- *Privacy Control:* Storing TBOMs off-ledger allows organizations to retain control over data privacy and access. Sensitive information can be kept off-chain, reducing the risk of data exposure while still leveraging blockchain's verification capabilities.
- *Flexibility in Storage Options:* Organizations can choose from various storage solutions—centralized, decentralized, or hybrid—based on specific requirements, such as cost, performance, security, and compliance needs.

Challenges associated with off-ledger TBOM distribution involve ensuring data integrity, managing synchronization between off-ledger data and on-chain proofs, and mitigating security risks associated with centralized storage systems. These challenges can impact the reliability and trustworthiness of off-ledger TBOM management, including:

- *Trust and Integrity Concerns:* Off-ledger methods lack the inherent immutability of blockchain, requiring additional safeguards such as regular audits and cryptographic proofs to ensure data integrity.
- *Synchronization Complexity:* Ensuring that off-ledger TBOM data remains synchronized with on-chain verification records can be technically challenging and may require smart contracts or automated processes.
- *Security Risks in Centralized Systems:* Centralized storage solutions may be vulnerable to breaches and data tampering. Decentralized solutions, while more secure, may have their own challenges related to data consistency and redundancy.
- *Compliance Requirements:* Off-ledger storage must still comply with various data protection regulations, requiring secure data management practices and robust access controls.

6.1.3 Hybrid Approaches: Combining On-Ledger and Off-Ledger

Hybrid approaches combine both on-ledger and off-ledger mechanisms, strategically distributing different parts of the TBOM data across both environments. Unlike off-ledger methods, which keep data entirely off-chain, hybrid models selectively utilize the blockchain for recording critical data points or cryptographic proofs while storing the bulk of the TBOM data in off-ledger environments. This method is designed to achieve a balance between cost efficiency, data privacy, scalability, and the trust and integrity of blockchain.

The benefits of hybrid approaches come from their ability to leverage both on-ledger and off-ledger advantages, balancing cost-efficiency, scalability, privacy, and security to create a flexible TBOM distribution strategy. Key benefits include:

- *Cost-Effective Security and Trust:* Hybrid approaches significantly reduce blockchain transaction costs by storing only essential proofs on-chain, while the bulk of the data remains off-ledger.
- *Enhanced Privacy and Control:* Sensitive data is stored off-ledger, minimizing exposure risks while leveraging blockchain's integrity checks to ensure that no unauthorized modifications have occurred.
- *Adaptability and Scalability:* Organizations can dynamically adjust the proportion of on-chain and off-ledger data based on current operational needs, regulatory requirements, or network conditions, providing greater flexibility.

However, hybrid approaches also face several challenges that must be carefully managed to optimize their effectiveness. These challenges often revolve around the complexity of integration, consistency management, and the need for robust security protocols. Key challenges include:

- *Complexity in Implementation:* Designing and maintaining a hybrid system requires careful integration of blockchain and off-chain storage solutions, smart contracts, and cryptographic protocols. This complexity can increase development time and costs.
- *Consistency and Synchronization Issues:* Ensuring that on-chain records and off-ledger TBOM data remain synchronized is a technical challenge. Any discrepancies could undermine the trust and reliability of the TBOM data. Automated synchronization mechanisms, such as smart contracts, are necessary to maintain data consistency.
- *Security Vulnerabilities:* While hybrid approaches balance privacy and transparency, they also create potential attack vectors that exploit the connection between on-chain and off-chain data. Ensuring end-to-end security and implementing measures such as encryption, secure access controls and regular audits are crucial.
- *Compliance Management:* Combining on-ledger and off-ledger storage may complicate compliance with various data protection and privacy regulations. Organizations must ensure that both data storage methods align with relevant legal requirements to avoid potential legal and financial repercussions.

Given the various advantages and challenges of both on-ledger and off-ledger TBOM distribution mechanisms, the RESCALE project benefits most from adopting a hybrid approach. This strategy provides the best of both worlds by balancing the transparency, immutability, and trust provided by on-ledger solutions with the flexibility, scalability, and cost-efficiency of off-ledger methods. The hybrid approach allows RESCALE to securely manage sensitive TBOM data off-ledger while using the blockchain to verify the integrity and authenticity of the data, ensuring robust supply chain security without compromising on performance or privacy. By dynamically adjusting the balance between on-chain and off-chain data storage, the hybrid model enables RESCALE to adapt to evolving operational needs and regulatory requirements, making it the most effective solution for modern supply chain challenges.

6.2 Smart Contracts for TBOM Management

Smart contracts provide an innovative approach to managing Trusted Bills of Materials (TBOMs) within supply chains by leveraging blockchain technology to automate, secure, and streamline various processes. There are two primary models for integrating smart contracts with TBOMs: the **Integrated TBOM model** and the **Externalized Asset TBOM model**. The Integrated TBOM model stores all relevant data on-chain, providing full transparency, immutability, and automation. In contrast, the Externalized Asset TBOM model balances blockchain's security benefits with the scalability, cost efficiency, and flexibility of off-chain storage solutions. This section explores both models and explains why the Externalized Asset TBOM model was chosen for the RESCALE project.

6.2.1 Integrated TBOM Model

The Integrated TBOM model involves managing the entire lifecycle of TBOMs directly on the blockchain. In this model, smart contracts handle the creation, validation, distribution,

and updating of TBOMs, ensuring all data is stored on-chain and accessible to authorized stakeholders. This approach provides the highest level of transparency, auditability, and trust.

- **Automated Validation and Distribution:** Smart contracts automatically validate TBOMs against predefined criteria such as component authenticity, compliance with industry standards, and data integrity using cryptographic hashes. Validated TBOMs are then distributed to relevant parties across the supply chain, ensuring all stakeholders access accurate and current information.
- **Real-Time Updates and Synchronization:** Changes to a TBOM, such as adding new components or updating existing ones, are instantly reflected on the blockchain, ensuring synchronization across the supply chain network and minimizing the risk of outdated data being used.
- **Access Control and Compliance:** Smart contracts enforce Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) or Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) to ensure that only authorized entities can interact with TBOM data. Additionally, the blockchain's immutability provides an audit trail for all TBOM transactions, facilitating regulatory compliance and enhancing transparency.

The Integrated TBOM model offers:

- **Full Automation and Trust:** Automating TBOM management processes through smart contracts reduces manual intervention and errors while building trust among supply chain partners.
- **Transparency and Traceability:** The blockchain records all changes and transactions, providing a comprehensive, immutable, and traceable history of the TBOM lifecycle.

However, the model also presents challenges:

- **Scalability and Performance:** Storing large volumes of data on-chain can cause performance bottlenecks and high transaction costs, especially on public blockchains.
- **Security and Maintenance:** Smart contracts require regular audits and updates to prevent vulnerabilities and align with evolving regulatory requirements.

6.3 Externalized Asset TBOM Model

The Externalized Asset TBOM model stores the actual TBOM data off-chain while using smart contracts to manage cryptographic proofs, references, and access controls. This approach addresses scalability and cost concerns by reducing the data stored on-chain and leveraging off-chain storage solutions.

- **Off-Chain Storage with On-Chain References:** TBOMs are stored in decentralized storage platforms like IPFS or centralized solutions like AWS S3. Smart contracts store cryptographic hashes or URIs on-chain, which serve as references to the off-chain data. This setup allows for efficient retrieval and verification of TBOMs without overwhelming the blockchain network.
- **Data Retrieval and Integrity Validation:** Stakeholders use smart contracts to obtain references to off-chain TBOMs stored in IPFS and validate their integrity by comparing the cryptographic hash of the retrieved data with the hash stored on-chain. IPFS generates a unique content identifier (CID) based on the TBOM data, which is then used as the hash reference in the blockchain for ensuring data integrity. The integrity validation process can be fully integrated into the RESCALE trusted storage system through the API, enabling automated hash verification and seamless interaction between the off-ledger storage and on-chain references.
- **Smart Contract-Based Access Controls:** Smart contracts enforce access control policies to ensure only authorized parties can retrieve or update TBOM data, allowing for more flexible and secure data management.

The Externalized Asset TBOM model provides:

- **Cost Efficiency and Scalability:** By storing only essential cryptographic proofs on-chain, the Externalized Asset TBOM model reduces transaction costs and improves scalability, making it suitable for environments with large datasets or frequent updates.
- **Enhanced Privacy and Flexibility:** Sensitive data remains off-chain, reducing exposure risks while still leveraging blockchain's verification and immutability features.
- **Redundancy and Data Availability:** Decentralized storage systems like IPFS provide redundancy and high availability, ensuring TBOM data remains accessible even during network failures.

Despite its advantages, this model also has challenges:

- **Consistency and Synchronization:** While the TBOM is generally static, there are specific use cases where updates may be required. For example, a TBOM includes a vulnerability document, new vulnerabilities can be added over time, necessitating updates in the IPFS-stored document and generating a new block in the blockchain to represent the updated vulnerability document's new hash. Similarly, if the TBOM is used to support code versioning or track changes to components, it becomes a dynamic document that requires synchronization between the off-chain storage and on-chain records to ensure consistency. In these scenarios, automated synchronization mechanisms are crucial to maintain data integrity and accurate record-keeping across environments.
- **Security Risks in Off-Chain Storage:** While off-chain storage offers flexibility, it introduces additional security risks that must be carefully managed to maintain the integrity and confidentiality of TBOM data. These risks include unauthorized access, data breaches, tampering, and data loss. Centralized storage systems, in particular, are vulnerable to attacks targeting the server infrastructure, which could compromise sensitive

information. Similarly, decentralized storage solutions, while more resilient against single points of failure, may suffer from issues like malicious node operators or inconsistent data availability. To mitigate these risks, organizations must implement robust encryption (both at rest and in transit), strict access control policies (e.g., Role-Based Access Control or Attribute-Based Access Control), regular security audits to identify potential vulnerabilities, and backup mechanisms to ensure data availability.

6.3.1 Rationale for Choosing the Externalized Asset Model

The RESCALE project chose the Externalized Asset TBOM model because it effectively balances the need for blockchain security with the flexibility and cost-efficiency of off-chain storage. This model addresses several key challenges:

- **Scalability and Performance:** It reduces on-chain data storage, avoiding performance bottlenecks and high transaction fees, making it suitable for managing large volumes of TBOM data.
- **Cost Efficiency:** By minimizing on-chain transactions, the model significantly reduces costs, allowing for sustainable scaling of operations.
- **Privacy and Flexibility:** Sensitive information remains off-chain, allowing for better data control and compliance with regulations like GDPR while still benefiting from blockchain's immutability for verification.
- **Integration and Maintenance:** The model integrates easily with existing supply chain management systems and allows for more straightforward updates, reducing complexity and maintenance efforts.

By leveraging the Externalized Asset TBOM model, RESCALE can achieve a robust, secure, and efficient supply chain management framework that aligns with the project's goals and adapts to evolving needs and challenges.

7 TBOM Security & Privacy

In this section access control, authenticity, integrity, proof of computation and privacy preserving technologies are discussed in the context of the TBOM, specifically describing options for the security and integrity of the TBOM document in the RESCALE platform, once the TBOM generator is operational. or as solutions to issues auxiliary to the TBOM.

7.1 TBOM Data Privacy

The first item of importance to mention is that the TBOM itself includes no personal identifying information or private data. In broader terms, the only private data stored by the wider RESCALE platform are the emails and usernames of the generators of documents such as the SSCG and DSCG, but this is not the purview of the TBOM and such data is not stored in this document. The TBOM is intended for viewing by end-users, but any desired privacy for TBOMs would be implemented at the storage-level and would not constitute actions within the document itself. The SSCG, DSCG, TBOM structure generated by the tools & the platform do not have any identification data aside from the email and username of the assessor/generator, the RESCALE platform does not provide source code. Presently, it is intended to leverage terms and conditions in end-user license agreements when users sign up to the RESCALE platform to enable the storing of the aforementioned generator details for the purpose of enforcing accountability by possess the authors' identities.

7.2 Access Control

To manage access control for a TBOM, several techniques can be employed. These techniques ensure that only authorized individuals or systems have access to the TBOM, maintaining its integrity and confidentiality. Here are some key access control techniques:

- **Role-Based Access Control (RBAC).** RBAC restricts access based on the roles assigned to users within an organization. It allows for fine-grained control by defining roles with specific permissions. Different roles such as developers, producers, and consumers can have varying levels of access to different parts of the TBOM, ensuring that only authorized roles can view or modify sensitive information. For instance, a developer may have full access to view and modify technical specifications, while a consumer can only view a finalized TBOM report without seeing proprietary supplier information.
- **Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC).** ABAC provides a more granular approach than RBAC by using attributes such as user roles, departments, and contextual factors (e.g., time of access). Access to the TBOM can be granted based on a combination of user attributes (e.g., department, job title) and environmental attributes (e.g., time of day, location). This method is especially useful when access needs to be restricted based on dynamic or context-driven attributes, such as location or device security state. For example, a supply chain manager may only be granted access to sensitive TBOM data when accessing the system from a secure company device during business hours.

- **Access Control Lists (ACLs).** ACLs can specify which users or systems can access specific parts of the TBOM stored in different locations, so it can provide a split-TBOM using Storage Access Control. Define ACLs for different segments of the TBOM, ensuring that only authorized users can access sensitive sections stored separately (e.g., purchased components vs. public components). In a large-scale supply chain, ACLs could be applied to manage access at the component level, so that certain suppliers can only access the sections of the TBOM relevant to the parts they supply.
- **Mandatory Access Control (MAC).** MAC ensures strict control over access based on predefined policies set by a central authority. It classifies data within the TBOM at different security levels (e.g., public, confidential) and enforces access based on these classifications. This could be used to enforce that only high-level auditors have access to confidential vulnerability information, while lower-level participants see only public details. This approach is particularly useful in heavily regulated industries where compliance requires strict access governance.
- **Discretionary Access Control (DAC).** DAC allows the owner of the TBOM to control access rights at a detailed level. The TBOM owner can define specific permissions for different users or groups, controlling who can access, modify or share various parts of the TBOM (Granular Access and Split-TBOM). For example, a manufacturer could create granular access rights allowing a partner organization to view specific sections of the TBOM, while restricting editing capabilities to internal teams. DAC is effective for Granular Access and Split-TBOM models, where different parts of the TBOM may require distinct levels of access.
- **Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA).** MFA adds an additional layer of security to ensure that only authorized users can access sensitive parts of the TBOM. It requires that users authenticate using multiple methods (e.g., password and one-time code) before accessing encrypted or sensitive parts of the TBOM. For instance, before a user can modify sensitive TBOM fields, they might need to authenticate using both a secure password and a mobile-based one-time code, further reducing the risk of unauthorized access.
- **Encryption and Digital Signatures.** Encrypting the TBOM ensures that only authorized users with the decryption key can read it. Digital signatures can verify the authenticity and integrity of the TBOM. It is also possible to encrypt sensitive parts of the TBOM while leaving public parts unencrypted (partial encryption). In a distributed supply chain, encryption ensures that if a TBOM is intercepted during transmission, unauthorized users cannot read its contents, while digital signatures maintain the integrity and authenticity of the document across multiple parties.

7.3 TBOM Integrity & Authenticity

Due to the inclusion of distributed ledger technologies in the WP4 technology stack, there is an implicit level of integrity assured. Beyond this, several integrity technologies are currently being explored to ensure the integrity of the TBOM, for example in T4.3 for trusted storage:

- **Digital signatures** would see relatively standard usage, primarily for signing documents such as the TBOM and the static and dynamic security test reports. Digital signatures

not only verify the authenticity of the TBOM but also ensure non-repudiation, preventing any party from denying their involvement in generating or modifying the TBOM. This level of assurance is particularly important when multiple parties collaborate in the supply chain, ensuring trust throughout the lifecycle. Real-world applications of digital signatures can be seen in software supply chains like those using the Linux Foundation's Sigstore, where cryptographic signatures are used to verify software components. In TBOM context, a similar approach could be adopted, ensuring that every modification to the TBOM is signed, timestamped and verifiable, thus creating a transparent audit trail of changes. Additionally, systems such as DocuSign implement digital signatures to ensure the integrity and authenticity of legal and compliance documents, which can be adapted to supply chain documentation like TBOMs.

- **Checksums** can offer integrity assurance for downloading documents from RESCALE's trusted storage. To further enhance integrity verification, cryptographic hash functions such as SHA-256 or SHA-3 could be employed for computing checksums, ensuring that any tampering or corruption of the documents is easily detectable.
- **Verified credentials** can link real-world users to an account on the RESCALE platform, which could be beneficial, for example, to identify testers. These verified credentials can be tied to specific roles within the supply chain, ensuring that only authorized personnel can sign, modify, or access certain TBOM details. Moreover, the use of decentralized identity systems, such as those following the W3C Verifiable Credentials standard, could add another layer of trust and decentralization, reducing reliance on central authorities while ensuring secure identification.
- **API Requirements**, for example specified in a JSON document, could be utilized interacting with Trusted Storage. Using APIs for interacting with trusted storage allows seamless integration between various supply chain tools and TBOM systems. APIs should also enforce strict authentication mechanisms such as OAuth 2.0 or token-based access (e.g., JWTs) to ensure that only authorized systems can interact with the TBOM, maintaining its integrity during any interaction.
- **TBOM fields** for storing hashes or transaction IDs, such as those from the previous TBOM version's block, could be beneficial for tracing back through the chain. By incorporating hash pointers or Merkle trees, the TBOM can efficiently maintain a tamper-evident chain of records. This would ensure that even if one block is compromised, it can be traced back, and any discrepancy would immediately be detected, further bolstering the trust and transparency of the TBOM.

7.4 Proof-of-Computation

In RESCALE architecture and design, it is decided to use blockchain technology to record all the transactions which are the security tests including the static code analysis and dynamic validation. Although the TBOM contains outputs of all those tests but there is a need to prove that specific tests/test sets were carried out on a software/hardware component. This can be done by exploiting the blockchain technology for proof of computation. Most popular approach is using Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZKP) technology integrated in the blockchain design and implementation to prove the validity of a computation. This section aims to do some SotA review on this topic and outline some possible solutions for RESCALE.

ZKP technologies - a Zero Knowledge Proof is a cryptographic technique that allows one party, e.g., the prover, to demonstrate to another party, e.g., the verifier, that they possess certain information without exposing the the actual details of that information. In other words, it can be used to provide proof of computation by allowing the prover to demonstrate that a computation was executed correctly without revealing information of that computation (e.g., inputs, intermediate steps, etc.). The technology relies on polynomial equations to ensure the accuracy and security of the computation. There are two well-known variations of the ZKP technology including the ZK-SNARK and ZK-STARK [37]. The ZK-SNARK was proposed first, and it is representing a general-purpose succinct non-interactive ZKP technology that can be used for many different use cases including verifiable computation and privacy-preserving cryptography. The keywords for this approach is succinct and non-interactive which mean the generated proof is small and quick to verify, and the prover and verifier do not need to interact with each other. However, this technology exposes many weaknesses, and one of them is its reliance to a trusted setup. The ZK-STARK was then proposed to resolve this weakness of ZK-SNARKs. Article [37] claims that ZK-STARK is secure even against attackers with quantum computers due to its pure rely on hashes and information theory. Some other flavors of ZKP include STARKs and Buleproofs. The main differences among those ZKP technologies are proof size, runtime (for generating and verifying proofs), and in the need for trusted setups. Below are some projects that incorporate ZKP.

Ethereum and ZK-EVM - The Ethereum [20] also leverages the ZKPs in their Ethereum Virtual Machine, which they call ZK-EVM, to make cryptographic proofs of computation. Previously, a smart contract can only access to current data but not the historical data (e.g., onchain data of past executions), and this has caused complication in proving some storage slots were used and computation was executed previously. To enable the ability to retrieve historical data, Ethereum introduced the BLOCKHASH opcode which let smart contracts to access past block data. In particular, this BLOCKHASH opcode receives a block number as input and output a hash of one of the 256 most recent complete blocks.

Axiom [9] and Herodotus [26] also integrate this approach together with ZKPs to provide smart contracts trustless access to historical data on the chain which also enable ability to provide proof of storage used in the Ethereum storage structure and proof of computation executed in the chain. In Axiom, it provides the Typescript software development kit (SDK) for developers to define their computations over onchain data they want to request from them. Then, it will send results on-chain with a ZK validity proof that the input data was correctly fetched, and the compute was correctly applied. This ZK validity proof is verified onchain in the smart contract. The result will then be sent to the chosen smart contract after this verification. The smart contract can then use the result as the on-chain data. For Herodotus, it is a middleware that provides smart contracts access to current and historical onchain data across Ethereum layers. Their offerings include the inclusion proofs which confirm data's presence and proofs of computation that validate the execution of some workflow to attest the validity of elements in a dataset.

Other projects have been built around the concept of ZK-EVMs, such as Polygon [43], zkSync [57], Linea [30], Scroll [47] and Taiko [52]. The main difference among them is the design where they have different trade-off between compatibility and performance. Their design and implementation can also be good references for RESCALE to offer its solutions for proof of computation in the TBOM.

Remote Attestation - Remote attestation [28] is a security technique for the verification of

integrity and trustworthiness of remote systems. It involves a verifier system, which requests evidence from a prover system in order to prove the security of the software and hardware on that system. Cryptographic methods are routinely used by the prover for this, such as signed configurations reports, which the verifier then compares with a trusted reference. The approach is frequently used in secure computing, such as cloud service providers, to ensure that critical operations are executed on verified systems. Remote attestation generally the prover must use a root of trust for the verifier to accept evidence from it. This approach enables the confirmation that a system has not been compromised.

RESCALE approach - To provide proof of computation in TBOM without exposing underlying data, RESCALE can further exploit either the ZKP technology or Remote Attestation approach, and will be working toward the selection and integration of this technology in its current design and implementation of the blockchain.

7.5 Privacy Preserving BOM

Privacy Preserving TBOM faces many significant challenges. For example, a generated TBOM might expose sensitive data such as supplier details and transaction information, and during a lifecycle of a TBOM, there is no guarantee that there are no tampering or unauthorised changes on the data or attributes inside that BOM. In addition, the system must adhere to relevant regulatory compliance for the entire TBOM's lifecycle. Providing privacy preserving TBOM is one of the key roles to build and maintain trust among supply chain partners. For that, RESCALE investigates several privacy preserving techniques to find the best fit in its design and implementation. Below is a summary of techniques for privacy preserving.

Anonymisation - This process involves removing personally identifiable information (PII) from data. Techniques such as data masking and differential privacy are commonly used. In data masking, certain attributes of PII are replaced with symbols like '*' or '-'. Differential Privacy, on the other hand, adds calibrated noise to sensitive data, making it difficult to draw inferences from the results. In addition to data masking, k-anonymity and l-diversity can be implemented to ensure that even when combining multiple attributes, no individual can be uniquely identified. This reduces the risk of indirect identification when TBOMs are shared across multiple parties.

Pseudonymisation - This process involves replacing PII with artificial identifiers or pseudonyms to disconnect the data from its subject. For instance, substituting a random name for an individual ensures the data is not linked to that individual. A further enhancement of this is dynamic pseudonymisation, where pseudonyms are periodically rotated or refreshed. This is particularly useful in TBOMs as it prevents adversaries from linking static identifiers across different versions of the TBOM, ensuring that long-term tracking of supply chain actors is avoided. Dynamic pseudonymisation also strengthens confidentiality by reducing the risk of correlating TBOM transactions over time.

Encryption - This process involves applying an algorithm and an encryption key to transform data into an unreadable format, e.g., encoded / encrypted data. The encoded data are then only be decoded using a description key. This process is called data decryption. There are two types of encryption: symmetric and asymmetric. In symmetric, the same key is used for encryption and decryption. In asymmetric, a pair of public key and private key is used where the public key

is used to encrypt the data and the private key is used to decrypt the encrypted data. Symmetric encryption is faster and more efficient than asymmetric encryption, but it requires secure key distribution, whereas asymmetric encryption offers an advantage in this area. In the context of TBOMs, hybrid encryption can be particularly effective. Symmetric encryption can be used to quickly secure large datasets within the TBOM, while asymmetric encryption is employed for securely exchanging the encryption keys across distributed supply chain entities. This ensures both efficiency and security in protecting sensitive supply chain data.

Data Sanitisation - This process involves permanent alteration or removal of sensitive data in a secure manner. It is to prevent unauthorised access or recovery of sensitive data. Some techniques can be applied for data sanitisation include data erasure (permanently deleting data), data redaction (removing the sensitive part within data), data masking and differential privacy. For TBOMs, secure disposal protocols should also be considered. These protocols ensure that any TBOMs or related sensitive data that have been temporarily stored on external systems are completely wiped after use. This minimizes the risk of data recovery from decommissioned systems, further enhancing the privacy and security of the supply chain.

Attribute-Based Encryption - This technique enables data encryption where access is granted based on specific attributes of the data recipient, such as roles or certifications. For TBOMs, attribute-based encryption can be used to encrypt sensitive information like supplier details or component vulnerabilities. For example, only certified supply chain auditors or regulatory authorities could access vulnerability data by meeting the required attributes (e.g., certifications, roles, etc.). A supplier in the TBOM might be able to access only the parts of the document that relate to them, while broader details about other suppliers or confidential components remain encrypted. This ensures flexible, attribute-based privacy control, where each party in the supply chain only accesses the information they are authorized to see, while still maintaining the overall functionality of the TBOM.

8 Conclusions & Future Steps

This section will conclude the document and describe the future work related to the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) which will be forthcoming as the RESCALE project progresses.

8.1 Conclusions

This document presented the TBOM Structure to a sufficient level of detail as to support technical work, such as the upcoming minimum viable product. The state-of-the-art, including a wide variety of technologies and BOM formats are discussed. The decision to select the CycloneDX BOM format, largely informed by the SotA review which was conducted, is also explained. Security considerations for the TBOM, security test reports, the TBOM lifecycle, as well as the related TBOM distribution mechanisms of RESCALE's trusted storage, are also discussed in detail. JSON was selected as the BOM exchange format, and information on versioning software was also presented. Additional scope remains for modifications and improvements to the work herein.

8.2 Future Steps

The TBOM specification is at a sufficient level of detail to support the development of the approaching first version minimum viable product. It is expected that some modifications to the TBOM could be required depending on findings during this work.

Presently the TBOM is presented in CycloneDX BOM format and JSON language, with a block architecture detailing the sections of the TBOM. Representing the TBOM in a neutral format, from which one could implement it in presumably any standard or format, has been explored and deemed as valuable in general, however for the MVP an immediately usable specification, such as we have developed here, was imperative. Utilizing the findings from this document in ongoing WP4 tasks, T4.2 and T4.3 will also make use of the practical specification produced herein.

Extending the CycloneDX schema is also of interest, and would be done by adding new types or extending existing types, for example to accommodate novel elements of the RESCALE SSCG and DSCG reports, or offer a more elegant solution for the trust assurance and testing proofs sections. These are present already in the TBOM specification under existing CycloneDX types, for the purposes of presenting a compiling, usable TBOM for the upcoming MVP. It is noted, however, that there could be significant benefit in extending CycloneDX with bespoke types that capture novel contributions from RESCALE.

9 Annex

This annex presents an example JSON program showing how an implementation of the Trusted Bill of Materials could look. This JSON was validated and compiled against a Python script including the CycloneDX library.

9.1 Annex I: TBOM Example JSON

```
{
  "serialNumber": "urn:uuid:856440af-7181-4293-b1f1-aade5c738a74",
  "version": 1,
  "$schema": "http://cyclonedx.org/schema/bom-1.6.schema.json",
  "bomFormat": "CycloneDX",
  "specVersion": "1.6",
  "components": [
    {
      "bom-ref": "sbom1-ref",
      "description": "SBOM for this TBOM",
      "externalReferences": [
        {
          "comment": "SBOM URL",
          "type": "distribution",
          "url": "https://rescale/sbom1/",
          "hashes": [
            {
              "alg": "SHA-256",
              "content": "c0fcf1d55386a4f260c46a0947
e24411a496646e69395dd84567c90fe043b957"
            }
          ]
        }
      ],
      "name": "SBOM1",
      "purl": "pkg:pypi/flask@3.0.1",
      "type": "file",
      "version": "1"
    },
    {
      "bom-ref": "bov1-ref",
      "description": "Continuously updated Bill of Vulnerabilities",
      "externalReferences": [
        {
          "comment": "Link to BOV",
          "type": "distribution",
          "url": "https://rescale/bov1/"
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

```

    ],
    "name": "BOV1",
    "purl": "pkg:pypi/flask-sqlalchemy@3.1.1",
    "type": "file",
    "version": "1"
  },
  {
    "bom-ref": "sscg1-ref",
    "description": "Static test report",
    "externalReferences": [
      {
        "comment": "SSCG link",
        "type": "static-analysis-report",
        "url": "https://rescale/sscg1/",
        "hashes": [
          {
            "alg": "SHA-256",
            "content": "64ec88ca00b268e5ba1a35678a
1b5316d212f4f366b2477232534a8aeca37f3c"
          }
        ]
      }
    ],
    "name": "SSCG1",
    "purl": "pkg:pypi/bcrypt",
    "type": "file"
  },
  {
    "bom-ref": "dscg1-ref",
    "description": "Dynamic test report",
    "externalReferences": [
      {
        "comment": "DSCG link",
        "type": "dynamic-analysis-report",
        "url": "https://rescale/dscg1"
      }
    ],
    "name": "DSCG1",
    "purl": "pkg:pypi/boto3",
    "type": "file"
  },
  {
    "bom-ref": "trustAssurance1",
    "description": "Combined has for linked files, hash of previous block",
    "name": "TrustAssurance",
    "purl": "pkg:pypi/botocore",
    "type": "cryptographic-asset",
    "hashes": [

```

```
        {
            "alg": "SHA-256",
            "content": "c8ceb5bb5b8bb75e64286541c1
2014b8600de29da6ca79b7464c0183f9906b6"
        }
    ]
},
{
    "bom-ref": "testingProof1",
    "description": "Combined hash, signature for linked files",
    "name": "TestingProof",
    "purl": "pkg:pypi/botocore",
    "type": "cryptographic-asset",
    "externalReferences": [
        {
            "comment": "Test proof link",
            "type": "distribution",
            "url": "https://rescale/testingProof1/",
            "hashes": [
                {
                    "alg": "SHA-256",
                    "content": "745e945081cc16d23aa371859e
6c8697fbbb4dabdc4164f6f4f2d0c806a52d3"
                }
            ]
        }
    ]
},
{
    "bom-ref": "extension-ref",
    "description": "Placeholder for future modification or extension",
    "externalReferences": [
        {
            "comment": "extension",
            "type": "distribution",
            "url": "https://rescale/extension/"
        }
    ],
    "name": "extension",
    "purl": "pkg:pypi/flask-login@0.6.3",
    "type": "data",
    "version": "1"
}
],
"dependencies": [
    {
        "ref": "sbom1-ref"
    },
],
```

```
{
  {
    "ref": "bov1-ref"
  },
  {
    "ref": "ssc1-ref"
  },
  {
    "ref": "dscg1-ref"
  },
  {
    "ref": "trustAssurance1-ref"
  },
  {
    "ref": "testingProof1-ref"
  },
  {
    "ref": "extension-ref"
  }
]
}
```

9.2 Annex II: TBOM Metadata Example JSON

```
"metadata": {
  "component": {
    "bom-ref": "tbom1-metadata",
    "name": "tbom1/metadata",
    "type": "file"
  },
  "supplier": {
    "name": "rescale-project"
  },
  "timestamp": "2024-09-24T13:20:53.367071+00:00",
  "tools": [
    {
      "name": "tbomgenerator",
      "vendor": "rescale-consortium."
    }
  ]
}
```

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